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CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D17: CODECO EdgeNet Framework Version 1.0

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Executive Summary

CODECO Deliverable D17 – *CODECO EdgeNet Framework* relates with the work under development in WP5 and Task 5.2 – *CODECO EdgeNet Framework*. This task is focused on leveraging the CODECO Experimentation Framework (CODEF) in order to validate CODECO aspects and support large-scale experimentation initiatives.

D17 provides a detailed overview of CODEF, including its design, architecture, and workflow. It details the rationale behind the decision to replace EdgeNet with CODEF; it also highlights the validation procedures for CODECO components and OSS, using CODEF. The document also outlines the methodology guidelines proposed in CODECO that can be integrated with CODEF, its contribution to reliably support CODECO experiments, selective explanations of the underlying code, and a set of proof-of-concept implementations that were carried out during the development of the framework.

Keywords: Experimentation, Framework, Evaluation

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```
#!/bin/bash
# generic configuration parameters - only if they are not already set
: ${admin_username:=athena} # define admin username
: ${admin_password:=ENCODED} # define sha-512 encoded password
: ${cloud_ip=10.0.1.1} # define cloud server IP
: ${cloud_name=my_cloud} # define name of cloud server
: ${cloud_operator:=infrastructure-manager-aws} # define infrastructure manager
: ${kubernetes_type=vanilla} # K8s edge distribution
: ${kubernetes_networkfabric=flannel} # CNI plugin
: ${node_osimage=ubuntu-22-clean} # define VM image name
: ${master_hosts='["hostm1"]'}
: ${master_ips='["10.0.0.1"]'}
: ${master_mac='["86:16:91:ec:09:01"]'}
: ${worker_hosts='["hostw1","hostw2"]'}
: ${worker_ips='["10.0.0.2","10.0.0.3"]'}
: ${worker_mac='["86:16:91:ec:09:05","86:16:91:ec:09:06"]'}
: ${app_names='["benchmarks"]'}
: ${app_scopes='["cluster"]'}
```

Figure 5: Example configuration file. 24

```
#!/bin/bash
# import basic cluster configuration options
configuration_file='configurations/aws-experimentation-cluster'
# kubernetes related configuration parameters
kubernetes_type=vanilla
kubernetes_networkfabric=calico
# application configuration
app_names='["docker", "helm", "prometheus-grafana-alert", "kube-burner"]'
app_scopes='["cluster", "cluster", "cluster", "cluster"]'
# import configuration
source import_configuration.sh
# deploy cluster
source cluster_deployment.sh
```

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Name	Image	Last started	Actions
codeco-experiments	-	40 seconds ago	[stop] [refresh] [trash]
infrastructure-manager-xcpng-1	swnuom/infrastructure-manager-xcpng	41 seconds ago	[stop] [refresh] [trash]
athw8-1	swnuom/resource-manager	40 seconds ago	[stop] [refresh] [trash]
athw3-1	swnuom/resource-manager	40 seconds ago	[stop] [refresh] [trash]
athm2-1	swnuom/resource-manager	40 seconds ago	[stop] [refresh] [trash]

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NAMESPACE	NAME	READY	STATUS	RESTARTS	AGE
cert-manager	cert-manager-655ff476d-zxn2f	1/1	Running	0	26m
cert-manager	cert-manager-cainjector-6654f55cb7-lj6n8	1/1	Running	0	26m
cert-manager	cert-manager-webhook-6db4d44ff-7rggz	1/1	Running	0	26m
default	netperf-host-r5vb7	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-host-tw1jd	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-host-z9vp5	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-7bb86f5cbf-2f97s	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-7bb86f5cbf-vqh94	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-f5bg5	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-fn8dr	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-gd62m	1/1	Running	0	18m
he-codeco-acm	acm-operator-controller-manager-75568d6b7d-phbv1	2/2	Running	0	27m
he-codeco-acm	acm-swm-app-backend	1/1	Running	0	2m25s
he-codeco-acm	acm-swm-app-front-end	1/1	Running	0	2m25s
he-codeco-mdm	freshness-connector-check-connection-75d498fc7d-9lpdp	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	k8s-connector-check-connection-5b9446648d-k7sh2	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	kubescape-connector-check-connection-78c56795cb-vmzt8	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-api-0	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-controller-0	1/1	Running	3 (12m ago)	15m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-kafka-0	1/1	Running	0	17m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-neo4j-0	1/1	Running	0	17m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-zookeeper-0	1/1	Running	0	17m
he-codeco-netma	c1-lpm-88b7ff96d-9sx5n	1/1	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-netma	c2-lpm-7478546bc8-6n58q	1/1	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-netma	kind-control-plane-lpm-67db47c77f-h7gc6	1/1	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-controller-7df785c975-xkwdb	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-controller-manager-5c7b4646bf-q6fq5	2/2	Running	1 (22m ago)	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-operator-7748d55c4d-qkxxw	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-switch-4m84g	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-switch-9p8d7	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-switch-k8cgh	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	mysql-pod	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	nemesis-5d88bbfc55-xf8xb	1/1	Running	0	18m
he-codeco-netma	prometheus-lpm-network-7f6dcf54f8-fgxb9	2/2	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-pdlc	gnn-controller-5f54d96856-svtcv	1/1	Running	0	11m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-ca-56ddfcd975-8ws4c	1/1	Running	0	12m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-dp-57756f8f66-f8v6d	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-gnn-inference-596f5b9cc-pw9s2	1/1	Running	0	11m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-r1-796559d96-z7q7d	1/1	Running	0	7m46s
he-codeco-swm	controller-manager-687478449d-6lxl5	2/2	Running	0	5m50s
he-codeco-swm	solver-6f8f47857f-9r68k	1/1	Running	0	5m50s
kepler	kepler-exporter-5w6ks	1/1	Running	0	2m31s
kepler	kepler-exporter-mb88g	1/1	Running	0	2m31s
kepler	kepler-exporter-pkhb8	1/1	Running	0	2m31s

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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
	Experiment ID	Partner Name	Number of Nodes Requested	Requested Start Date	Requested End Date	Duration (in days)	Status	Experiment Outcome	Code / URL
1	ATH1	George Koukis (ATH)	3	9/11/2024	9/12/2024	14	Completed	CODEF integration to Shared Cloud	

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(a) Throughput performance on UDP (b) RAM utilization on UDP (c) CPU utilization on UDP

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```

athena@athml:~$ kubectl get nodes -o wide
NAME                STATUS    ROLES    AGE   VERSION   INTERNAL-IP   OS-IMAGE          KERNEL-VERSION
athml               Ready    control-plane, 28h   v1.23.17  83.2          Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS 5.15.0-71-generic
                    master
athw2               Ready    <none>   28h   v1.23.17  83.2          Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS 5.15.0-71-generic
athw3               Ready    <none>   28h   v1.23.17  83.2          Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS 5.15.0-71-generic
gr-a-7230.edge-net.io Ready    <none>   15m   v1.23.17  83.2          Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS 5.15.0-86-generic
gr-b-89c3.edge-net.io Ready    <none>   108s   v1.23.17  195.2        Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS 5.15.0-71-generic
gr-b-abf4.edge-net.io Ready    <none>   3m26s   v1.23.17  195.2        Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS 5.15.0-71-generic

athena@athml:~$ kubectl get nodecontributions
NAME    ADDRESS    PORT  ENABLED  STATUS    AGE
gr-a-7230  83.2      22    true     Node Accessed  16m
gr-b-89c3  195.2    22    true     Node Accessed  2m34s
gr-b-abf4  195.2    22    true     Node Accessed  4m13s
    
```

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Manager
AD	Anomaly Detection
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CP	Change Point
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/ Continuous Deployment
CIS	Center for Internet Security
CLI	Command Line Interface
CNI	Container Network Interface
CODECO	Cognitive, Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CODEF	CODECO Experimentation Framework
CP	Change Point
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
DD	Detection Delay
DEV	Developer
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter
ECI	Edge Cloud Infrastructure
GA	Grant Agreement
GEN	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Horizon Europe
HostGW	Host Gateway
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
IM	Infrastructure Manager
IAM	Identity Access Management
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IPIP	IP-in-IP
IPsec	Internet Protocol Security
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
K8s	K8s
KinD	K8s in Docker
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L2S-M	Link-Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms
MDM	Metadata Manager

MTU	Maximum Transmission Unit
ML	Machine Learning
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OS	Operating System
OSS	Open-Source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
RTT	Round Trip Time
SDN	Software Defined Network
SSH	Secure Shell
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VXLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
WG	Wireguard
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

This deliverable's goal is to provide a comprehensive overview of the work conducted between months 7 and 24 of the CODECO project [1], with emphasis on the contributions of the ATH partner within WP5 – *Experimentation Framework, Demonstrations and AI Data Governance and Resilience Testing* and Task 5.2. – *CODECO EdgeNet Framework*. A particular focus is given on the design, architecture and functionalities of the CODECO Experimentation Framework (CODEF) that render CODEF a novel CODECO asset; we highlight its value and justify its role as a replacement for EdgeNet, which was initially selected by the consortium for large-scale experimentation across diverse environments.

The initial experimentation plan of CODECO and WP5 assumed EdgeNet as the appropriate tool to enable the research community and developers to test CODECO components and OSS using the global open-source EdgeNet testbed. The purpose was to facilitate experimentation via the community-contributed nodes and novel EdgeNet features/Custom Resources (CRs). Furthermore, it was expected that EdgeNet would have allowed CODECO use cases to be validated in various globally distributed environments and hardware configurations.

However, the functionality and experimentation capabilities of EdgeNet relied on the infrastructure's availability and operational status. Persistent issues with the functionality of the testbed led ATH to develop a custom "CODECO-EdgeNet" version, which enabled the deployment of clusters utilizing some of EdgeNet's novel features. While this custom version is now outdated, it remains integrated into CODEF. Despite these efforts, ongoing challenges with the supporting software ultimately rendered EdgeNet unsuitable for extensive and wide-scale use; in turn, those limitations called for a new design and the consequent development of CODEF.

Serving as a replacement for EdgeNet, CODEF aims to deliver a robust, scalable, and flexible framework that supports diverse experimentation scenarios, including large-scale experimentations that ensure alignment of CODECO deliverables with CODECO's objectives and KPIs.

1.1 Document Scope

This deliverable is aligned with the objectives of Task 5.2 – CODECO EdgeNet Framework, involving the design of an experimentation framework suitable for testing and validating various CODECO components based on pre-selected use cases, and enable partners to deploy large-scale experiments across multiple domains. Additionally, CODEF facilitates automated and dynamic service management across Edge-Cloud environments, supporting both single- and future multi-cluster deployments endeavours. This deliverable provides:

- A detailed overview of the CODEF architecture, key features, workload, code description and examples, along with its integration with the CODECO OSS and its components.
- A description of the evaluation plan and processes, covering the deployment of CODECO OSS, identification of issues and their resolution.
- A plan for implementing guidelines and methodologies from CODECO deliverables, with reference to KPIs and validation metrics.
- Proofs-of-concept and valuable results showcasing CODEF functionalities and initial experimentation outcomes related to CODECO.

1.2 Document Structure

This document is organized as follows:

- **Section 1** outlines the overall scope, structure, and goals of the deliverable.
- **Section 2** discusses CODEF, EdgeNet and other European and global large-scale Edge-Cloud experimentation initiatives.
- **Section 3** summarizes the CODEF architecture, key features, workload, and its integration within CODECO. This section also includes architecture and sequence diagrams.
- **Section 4** expands on methodologies from Deliverables *D10 – CODECO Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design* [2] and *D15 – AI Governance and Resilience Aspects in CODECO* [3], focusing on experimentation aspects, relevant KPIs, and key validation metrics.
- **Section 5** details the deployment and validation of CODECO OSS and application, including issue tracking, management, and closure via the ECL GitLab.
- **Section 6** describes the AWS CODECO shared cloud space as well as on-premises testbeds, and equipment used within CODECO use cases.
- **Section 7** showcases proof-of-concept experiments using CODEF highlighting its features and utilization in CODECO and the Cloud-Edge.
- **Section 8** lists our conclusions and outlines future directions of CODEF and CODECO validation.

2 CODEF, EdgeNet and Large-Scale Edge-Cloud Experimentation Initiatives

Open testbeds play a crucial role in facilitating the deployment and validation of edge-cloud systems across various domains, including CEI, 5G/6G, distributed and cloud computing, ML and AI. They provide shared, controlled and flexible environments for evaluating novel technologies and systems, enabling researchers and stakeholders to collaborate effectively experiment with diverse scenarios, and validate performance under real-world conditions. Therefore, they bridge the gap between theoretical research and application deployments.

For instance, the **SLICES** testbed¹ (formerly Fed4FIRE+) integrates a variety of large-scale testbeds and simulators/emulators combining diverse experimentation platforms across Europe, focusing on networking protocols, wireless radio and 5/6G technologies (e.g., **Testlab** and **OfficeLab**², **Colosseum** [4]), cloud-edge infrastructures (e.g., **Virtual Wall**³) and IoT/smart city testbeds (e.g., **CityLab**⁴, **IoT Lab**⁵). Similarly, the USA-based **FABRIC**⁶ (formerly GENI) interconnects USA and global testbeds, such as **Emulab**⁷, **CloudLab**⁸ and **Chameleon**⁹ to support multi-cluster deployments and global-scale experimentation in areas such as distributed and edge computing or smart cities.

¹ <https://www.slices-ri.eu/>

² <https://doc.ilabt.imec.be/ilabt/wilab/index.html>

³ <https://doc.ilabt.imec.be/ilabt/virtualwall/>

⁴ <https://doc.lab.cityofthings.eu/wiki/>

⁵ <https://iotlab.com/>

⁶ <https://fabric-testbed.org/>

⁷ <https://www.emulab.net/>

⁸ <https://www.cloudlab.us/>

⁹ <https://chameleoncloud.org/>

Many testbeds offer tools to simplify resource discovery and allocation, such as jFed CLI¹⁰, geni-lib¹¹, and GENI OMNI¹², while some also incorporate APIs for experimentation control alongside web-based GUIs, as seen in platforms like Emulab and CloudLab. Tools like Ansible and Kubespray¹³, or Crossplane¹⁴ further facilitate software deployment automation. For instance, **CloudNativeLab**¹⁵ enables users to create Kubernetes clusters on SLICES testbeds using predefined resource configurations, providing VPN access, Kubernetes configurations, and deployment tools like Helm and *kubectl*. Additionally, testbeds like FABRIC offer open public metrics through Grafana, optical data, and latency services, allowing users to analyse such measurements. By leveraging hard-disk imaging and time-sharing models, testbeds allow experiments to be switched ON or OFF, optimizing resource utilization. These infrastructure-as-a-service capabilities, coupled with reusable tools, management portals and APIs, provide higher-level abstractions, ensuring flexibility, scalability, and adaptability across diverse experimentation scenarios.

A Kubernetes-centred solution is the recently introduced **ClusterSlice**¹⁶ platform, which not only provides a zero-touch approach to transforming testbed resources into fully operational K8s slices but also jointly utilizes and federates some of the above-mentioned testbeds.

EdgeNet¹⁷, an evolution of PlanetLab, is another testbed, adopting a crowd-sourcing model where users and institutions can contribute nodes, focusing on federated heterogeneous infrastructures. It targets globally distributed edge-cloud environments using Kubernetes-native deployments and node contribution processes enhanced with CRs and testbed control features. Through a web-based interface and user-specific configurations, EdgeNet provides RBAC and permission management using user-specific kubeconfig files and RoleBinding K8s objects. It also offers novel features such as selective deployment and location-based node selection, slicing, and isolation of experiments in dedicated namespaces.

CODECO adopts a cross-layer adaptation approach, aiming to ensure enhanced performance for microservice-based applications across the entire Edge-Cloud continuum. CODECO introduces novel components, including ACM for automated configuration, deployment and monitoring of edge cloud resources, MDM for data workflow observability, SWM for scheduling and re-scheduling of application workloads, PDLC taking intelligent decisions for edge cloud orchestration, and NetMA providing network-awareness to CODECO and handling secure connectivity across pods. From this point of view, an edge cloud continuum experimentation framework should be able to (i) incorporate holistic experimental definitions for all layers of the protocol stack and main K8s features, including the support of alternative edge infrastructures and virtualization technologies and accommodate the diversity of edge cloud demands; ii) simplify experimentation through well-designed abstractions; iii) advance automation and reliability, for executing experiments across varying cross-layer parameters; and (iv) support modular extensions for flexible, scalable deployments.

Initially, CODECO aimed to use **EdgeNet** as a testbed for large-scale, multi-tenant experimentation. This approach involved leveraging the community's contributed nodes in EdgeNet to create customized workloads that simulate real user interactions with CODECO.

¹⁰ <https://jfed.ilabt.imec.be/>

¹¹ <https://geni-lib.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹² <https://fed4fire.eu/tools/omni/index.html>

¹³ <https://kubespray.io/>

¹⁴ <https://www.crossplane.io/>

¹⁵ <https://practicum.cloudnativelab.ilabt.imec.be/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/SWNRG/clusterslice/>

¹⁷ <https://www.edge-net.org/>

For example, during benchmarking, workloads could be generated using EdgeNet-hosted clients selected based on specific criteria, such as geo-location. To support this effort, both ATH and FOR contributed one node each to facilitate these tests. However, due to strict limitations with the **EdgeNet infrastructure** in accessing and executing experiments across the testbed, software updates provided by partner ATH offered the deployment option of “CODECO-EdgeNet” clusters that integrate some of the inherent EdgeNet features i.e. multi-tenancy and multi-provider. The former provided different cluster management options such as tenant and role requests, slices and sub-namespaces, while the latter allowed to contribute nodes (VMs or physical machines) into a unified “CODECO-EdgeNet” cluster with a simple bootstrap script. **Besides the effort, the experimentation and functionality of the different features within the EdgeNet testbed was not possible to disengage experiments from the temporary discrepancies or current limitations of the EdgeNet infrastructure.** Challenges such as versioning inconsistencies, compatibility issues, update delays, and underdeveloped federated features, along with limited support and repository deprecation necessitated the exploration of alternative solutions and led to the development of the **CODEF** [5] by ATH within WP5.

CODEF is an innovative, open-source experimentation tool extending existing approaches to provide a comprehensive, flexible framework for diverse resources across heterogeneous infrastructures via its abstraction layers. It extends the novel Resource and Infrastructure Manager operators of ClusterSlice, enabling their use as non-Kubernetes components. These abstractions manage the manipulation of VMs and compute resources, respectively. In comparison to ClusterSlice, CODEF is more lightweight – requiring only Docker for execution – and supports additional edge capabilities and environments, along with advanced experimentation automation features. It enables reproducible experiment deployment via declarative specifications, leveraging technologies such as Bash scripting, Ansible, and SSH for seamless orchestration. CODEF automates the entire experimentation process, from node allocation and OS deployment to application installation and results acquisition, making it a versatile solution for both single and multi-cluster domains. Inspired by the EdgeNet multi-tenant capability, CODEF designs a Node Contribution feature which inherently enables the creation and management of a shared cloud space. Its goal in the CODECO project is two-fold: **(i) Validation**, i.e., by deploying and evaluating CODECO OSS and its components within single or multi-cluster environments; and **(ii) Large-Scale Experimentation**, i.e., by overcoming EdgeNet’s limitations to providing a robust platform for scalable and flexible experimentation. This way, CODEF guarantees alignment with the project’s goals and KPIs in diverse scenarios. Further details on installing and running CODECO components through CODEF are available in Section 3.3.

3 CODECO Experimentation Framework (CODEF)

CODEF is a novel valuable asset, introduced within the CODECO project, replacing EdgeNet which was initially scheduled to be the foundation for scalable experimentation in WP5. While CODEF supersedes EdgeNet, it incorporates an outdated customized version of it. CODEF leverages a microservice-based architecture and introduces advanced abstractions aimed at reducing experimentation complexity, increasing automation, and improving reliability to address potential failures in diverse and heterogeneous requirements of edge-cloud environments. This makes CODEF a key enabler for advancing experimentation efforts in WP5, while also aiming to address aspects of the multi-cluster and federated experimentation of WP4. Furthermore, CODEF can support the development of methodologies that fully utilize the assets within the CODECO project. To assist the overall wide validation of CODECO, currently, **components such as the ACM and the L2S-M solution** (part of the NetMA component) **are already integrated into CODEF**. CODEF is also **available to the consortium within the CODECO shared Cloud space infrastructure** (rf. to Section 6.1.2). As an open-source solution, CODEF is hosted in the [Experimentation Framework project](#) within the CODECO ECL GitLab repository (rf. to Figure 1).

Figure 1: Experimentation framework GitLab repository

3.1 Key Features and Functionalities

CODEF offers a comprehensive and automated solution for the entire experimentation lifecycle within containerized environments, offering a holistic, declarative, and modular approach. Its main capabilities are: **(i) infrastructure as-a-service**, utilizing heterogeneous physical and virtual resources including open testbed infrastructures and virtualization systems; **(ii) platform-as-a-service**, deploying multiple composable Kubernetes flavours and network plugins for intra-cluster and inter-cluster communication; **(iii) application as-a-service**, allowing plug-and-play application features and experimentation software based on Ansible; and **(iv) experimentation automation**, including the execution of automated research experiments on topics like Kubernetes networking [6] and AD workflows [7],[8]. CODEF represents each node as a container that deploys and configures systems in parallel and with zero-touch provisioning. It also provides full node access for experimenters and the ability to declaratively define multiple Kubernetes clusters and experimentation applications.

Below is an overview of CODEF's key functionalities and features, however for a more comprehensive explanation, users can refer to the detailed documentation available in the [docs README](#):

- **Reproducible and scalable experimentation across diverse systems and environments** via the different Infrastructure Managers for the integration with external edge environments and testbeds, such as EdgeNet and Cloudlab. Additionally, it supports virtualization environments like XCP-ng¹⁸ and VirtualBox¹⁹, and can enable **multi-cluster and multi-domain capabilities** utilizing third-party tools like Liqo²⁰ and OCM²¹.
- **One-liner declarative end-to-end experimentation automation**, for the entire experimentation lifecycle from cluster deployment to experiment execution and results processing utilizing the modular abstraction layers to simplify the configuration and execution.
- **Low level configurable parametrization**, allowing users to define parameters such as protocol selection, security features and versioning according to specific experimental needs.
- **Advanced tracking and analytics functionalities**, including built-in tracking and real-time analytics to enhance observability with Jaeger²², deployment times and time-per-task as well as results statistics (e.g., mean and median values), enabling detailed performance evaluations.
- **Minimal operational support and need for backup** since the clusters and deployments can be easily removed and then re-configured from scratch (also including VM snapshots) to ensure quick clean installations.
- **Node contribution capabilities**, by allowing users to contribute nodes (virtual machines or bare-metal) to create shared environments and to facilitate collaborative experimentation and resource sharing, providing a flexible and scalable experimentation ecosystem.
- **Integration with EdgeNet**, by enabling the deployment of a custom EdgeNet cluster through CODEF and by providing multi-tenancy features for shared cluster management such as RBAC and resource slicing, as well as multi-provider support, allowing nodes to join a shared cluster with a one-liner script. However, as highlighted in Section 2, the availability and functionality of these features are subject to the current status and updates of EdgeNet.

3.2 Architecture

The architecture of CODEF is composed of several key components, as illustrated in Figure 2. Each component is implemented as an independent microservice (i.e., deployed as containers), ensuring modularity, flexibility, and extensibility. This design allows the framework to seamlessly integrate additional technologies or features as needed. The components are structured as distinct abstraction layers, described in detail in the following subsections. In summary, the components are as follows:

- **Infrastructure Managers:** Allocate cluster nodes over heterogeneous systems, including bare-metal physical nodes or virtual machines and cloud testbeds.
- **Resource Managers:** Oversee the automated deployment of software and applications on allocated nodes based on custom Ansible playbook templates.
- **Experiment Controller:** Automates experiments' execution by managing experiment definitions, metrics collection and result generation.
- **Results Processor:** Evaluates, post-processes, and visualizes experiment results, offering statistical analysis and report generation.

¹⁸ <https://xcp-ng.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.virtualbox.org/>

²⁰ <https://liqo.io/>

²¹ <https://open-cluster-management.io/>

²² <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

Figure 2: CODEF functional architecture.

3.2.1 Infrastructure Managers

The **Infrastructure Managers** (IMs) realize a technology-agnostic abstraction over heterogeneous testbeds and cloud systems. It is responsible for the entire process of cluster node allocation, from the provisioning of physical nodes or VMs to the installation of OS utilizing technologies like Bash scripting and the K8s bootstrapping tool, *kubeadm*. This is important for the deployment of experiments across diverse infrastructure setups without requiring extensive platform-specific configurations. Specifications such as the number of master and worker nodes, the choice of OS image, and the use of snapshots, serve as input to the IM, which outputs the addresses of the allocated physical nodes or VMs.

Currently, CODEF supports [three IM](#) i.e. (i) **XCP-ng**, for Xen-based orchestration; (ii) **VirtualBox**, for local cluster deployments; and (iii) **AWS**, related to the CODECO shared cloud infrastructure and the Experimentation cluster detailed in Section 6.1.2. However, users also have the flexibility to create custom IMs to support additional systems for their specific experimental needs.

Once an IM is created – following a similar approach to the already existing IMs as in [infrastructure-manager-xcpng](#) (i.e. building a Docker image and utilizing associated scripts) – it is specified in the relevant [configurations files](#) as “cloud_operator”. These configuration files are subsequently included in the corresponding experiment installation scripts such as the [install-cluster.sh](#).

3.2.2 Resource Managers

The **Resource Managers** serve as a node-level automation abstraction for managing the deployment of software across cluster nodes. They facilitate the deployment of user-defined applications, leveraging custom Ansible playbook templates to support a wide variety of software while managing version control and deployment scope i.e. deployment at the cluster level, across all nodes, or limited to master or worker nodes.

Through Ansible playbooks, CODEF enables the deployment of a range of software including: **(i) container orchestration and runtime environments**, including Kubernetes and Docker, along with various distributions such as vanilla K8s, and edge-related such as K3s, K0s, and MicroK8s; **(ii) deployment tools** like Argo and Helm; **(iii) networking solutions**, including a range of Container Network Interface (CNI) plugins and the L2S-M CODECO component (standalone installation); **(iv) monitoring and observability tools**, such as Prometheus, Grafana and dashboards; **(v) multi-cluster management software** (OCM, Ligo, Karmada, Submariner); and **(vi) load/stressing tools**, such as Kube-burner²³. A complete list of supported software is available in the [playbooks directory](#).

The supported software can be extended through custom playbooks, enabling the deployment of a wide range of applications – from observability and stress tools to more complex and demanding software like the CODECO framework or standalone components and EdgeNet. Once cluster nodes are allocated, a dedicated Resource Manager is deployed for each node to ensure efficient software deployment and management.

3.2.3 Experiment Controller

The **Experiment Controller** serves as a key component with the task of executing specific experiments once the cluster is operational. It provides an automated approach to conduct experiments without manual configuration, thus reducing complexity and ensuring consistency and reproducibility. To initiate an experiment, the user simply provides as input a definition that includes the name of the specific Experiment Controller to use, along with parameters such as the software/tool to be utilized e.g., a benchmarking tool, variables that may vary with each execution, metrics to be gathered e.g., CPU, RAM usage, throughput etc., and the desired number of replications. Subsequently, the framework utilizes the Experiment controller and related scripts e.g., [experiments controller.sh](#), to deploy a cluster for each run with a clean installation based on the parameters outlined in the script, to execute the experiments, generating the corresponding results and to store them within a directory named after the experiment. An example of this automated experimentation conducted with the experiment controller include the evaluation of CNIs and K8s distributions or AD workflows based on resource consumption network performance can be found in the [execute-plugins-experiment.sh](#) script. The obtained results can be visualized and formatted for clarity, allowing subsequent analysis through the Results Processor.

3.2.4 Results Processor

Finally, the **Results Processor** is the component responsible for the evaluation, post-processing, and presentation of the experimental outcomes. It plays a key role in transforming raw experimental data into valuable insights through a series of automated steps, ensuring that results can be easily analysed, shared or integrated as part of a more extensive future analysis. Specifically, the Results Processor performs tasks such as statistical analysis – calculating metrics like mean, median, and standard deviation – to assess the overall performance. Furthermore, the Results Processor automates the creation of LaTeX-based PDF reports. These reports incorporate the generated plots, statistical summaries, and other essential information, ensuring that experimental results are organized and ready for presentation/publication. This feature reduces manual report preparation, saving significant time and effort for researchers and developers.

²³ <https://kube-burner.github.io/kube-burner/>

3.3 Workload Deployment

This section focuses on the workload deployment process in CODEF, supported by figures illustrating its architecture and operational flow. It details the dependencies, setup procedures, and cluster deployment phases, users follow from repository cloning and configuration parameter definition to application installation and result analysis. Figure 3 illustrates the core components of CODEF and their interactions within the deployment process, showcasing the modular and containerized structure which enables scalability and flexibility. Note that all components take the form of microservices (i.e., containers) and can be independently extended to accommodate additional technologies or features. Furthermore, the CODEF sequence diagram (rf. to Figure 4) provides a detailed overview of user interactions and system actions. Specifically, the grey section outlines the streamlined process, detailing the steps users take to install CODEF, define cluster deployment parameters, execute experiments, and acquire results. Meanwhile, the yellow section illustrates the execution of processes on the system side (i.e., CODEF), showcasing its abstraction layers and their functionality during each phase, as described in the workload diagram (Figure 3).

Figure 3: CODEF abstraction layers and workload.

Figure 4: CODEF sequence diagram for users and CODEF/system actions.

3.3.1 Dependencies and Setup Phase

CODEF is designed for simplicity and experiment automation, requiring minimal dependencies to get started. To deploy and run CODEF, the user needs to:

1. Clone the [CODEF repository](#) on a system running Ubuntu 22.04.
2. Install the following prerequisites:
 - a. Docker
 - b. Jq (command-line JSON processor)
3. Set up password-less SSH access to the nodes intended for cluster deployment. For this case there is the [ssh without password.sh](#) script which saves the nodes' information to the `.ssh/authorized_keys`.

After ensuring the necessary requirements, the user can proceed with the cluster configuration parameters.

The [example-configuration](#) such as the one in Figure 5 will be used by the installation/experiment scripts to figure out where the nodes should be placed, defining

parameters like the (i) user's credentials, (ii) selected IM, (iii) name, IP and MAC addresses of the control plane (master) and worker nodes, and (iv) the OS to be taken as template for the VM creation from scratch.

```
#!/bin/bash
# generic configuration parameters - only if they are not already set
: ${admin_username:=athena} # define admin username
: ${admin_password:=ENCODED} # define sha-512 encoded password
: ${cloud_ip=10.0.1.1} # define cloud server IP
: ${cloud_name=my_cloud} # define name of cloud server
: ${cloud_operator:=infrastructure-manager-aws} # define infrastructure manager
: ${kubernetes_type=vanilla} # K8s edge distribution
: ${kubernetes_networkfabric=flannel} # CNI plugin
: ${node_osimage=ubuntu-22-clean} # define VM image name
: ${master_hosts='["hostm1"]'}
: ${master_ips='["10.0.0.1"]'}
: ${master_mac='["86:16:91:ec:09:01"]'}
: ${worker_hosts='["hostw1", "hostw2"]'}
: ${worker_ips='["10.0.0.2", "10.0.0.3"]'}
: ${worker_mac='["86:16:91:ec:09:05", "86:16:91:ec:09:06"]'}
: ${app_names='["benchmarks"]'}
: ${app_scopes='["cluster"]'}
```

Figure 5: Example configuration file.

Within the [cluster_deployment.sh](#) script, users can customize the deployment process by enabling or disabling core CODEF functionalities and features. These include:

- i) generating the *docker-compose.yaml* with the IM and cluster configurations.
- ii) enabling or disabling the DHCP service for deployments where the cloud server and CODEF are running on machines in different networks).
- iii) integrating Jaeger for enhanced observability and monitoring.

Finally, users can create an installation script like the one in Figure 6, in which they can import basic cluster configuration options like the [example-configuration](#), can change the K8s configuration parameters such as the K8s distribution and CNI plugin. Finally, they define the application configuration i.e. the SW or applications to be deployed – based on the custom Ansible [playbook templates](#) – with their respective scope i.e. at what level they should be deployed (master, worker, cluster or all).

```
#!/bin/bash
# import basic cluster configuration options
configuration_file='configurations/aws-experimentation-cluster'
# kubernetes related configuration parameters
kubernetes_type=vanilla
kubernetes_networkfabric=calico
# application configuration
app_names='["docker", "helm", "prometheus-grafana-alert", "kube-burner"]'
app_scopes='["cluster", "cluster", "cluster", "cluster"]'
# import configuration
source import_configuration.sh
# deploy cluster
source cluster_deployment.sh
```

Figure 6: Example *install-cluster.sh* installation script.

3.3.2 Cluster Deployment and Execution Phase

After the definition of the configuration parameters a user can deploy a new cluster or execute experiments by simply running the respective scripts. The ATH team has prepared some [example scripts](#) so users can experiment with some CODEF proof-of-concepts. These scripts (rf. to Table 1) demonstrate key features and capabilities of CODEF in various scenarios, providing a starting point for experimentation using CODEF.

Table 1: Description of CODEF example script files.

Script	Description
install-cluster.sh	Simple cluster deployment with vanilla K8s, Flannel CNI plugin and k8s-bench-suite as benchmark tool.
install-acm-cluster.sh	Cluster deployment with CODECO OSS installed.
install-l2sm-cluster.sh	Cluster deployment with standalone L2S-M component.
install-microk8s-cluster.sh	Cluster deployment with MicroK8s edge distribution.
execute-plugins-experiment.sh	Experiment script for CNI plugins' comparison within vanilla K8s with k8s-bench-suite as benchmark tool.
execute-k8s-distros-experiment.sh	Experiment script for CNI plugins' comparison across different (edge) distributions with k8s-bench-suite as benchmark tool.
execute-range-nodes-experiment.sh	Experiment script for CNI plugins' comparison across different nodes with k8s-bench-suite as benchmark tool.

When executing an installation or experiment script, CODEF dynamically creates the necessary images (e.g., Infrastructure and Resource Managers). **Docker images are locally compiled and built** (not pulled by a public external registry), allowing users to customize them based on their specific experiment needs and ensuring compatibility with different configurations. Each cluster node is represented as a Docker container. As depicted in Figure 7, this example cluster consists of three nodes, each **represented as a container** named according to the configuration, alongside the respective IM. This modular and containerized representation ensures scalability, flexibility and ease of deployment during experimentation.

Name	Image	Last started	Actions
codeco-experiments	-	40 seconds ago	Stop, Refresh, Delete
infrastructure-manager-xcpng-1	swnuom/infrastructure-manager-xcpng	41 seconds ago	Stop, Refresh, Delete
athw8-1	swnuom/resource-manager	40 seconds ago	Stop, Refresh, Delete
athw3-1	swnuom/resource-manager	40 seconds ago	Stop, Refresh, Delete
athm2-1	swnuom/resource-manager	40 seconds ago	Stop, Refresh, Delete

Figure 7: CODEF cluster nodes representation as containers in Docker Desktop.

From the user's perspective, the process is simplified to executing a single (installation or experiment) script. During the execution of the script, the user can monitor the entire process in real-time through the Ansible visualizer (rf. to Figure 8). This provides a detailed view of the progression, displaying the completion of each "Task" for every node in the cluster, along with the time required for each step. For instance, the user can observe the following stages: **(i) Node Creation**, i.e. each node or VM is created from scratch using the provided OS image or snapshot. The nodes are booted up based on the selected IM and admin credentials; **(ii) Cluster Preparation**, i.e. configuration files, keys, *kubectl* and *containerd* are generated to prepare the cluster environment; **(iii) Cluster Deployment**, i.e. deployed according to the configuration parameters defined by the user, including the choice of Kubernetes distribution

and network fabric or CNI; **(iv) Application Installation**, i.e. installed via the Resource Manager, utilizing custom Ansible playbook files and specifying the defined scope and application version.

By adopting this approach, CODEF **abstracts the complexity of configurations** and provides a simplified way to deploy and execute experiments. This ensures accessibility for users, even for those with minimal experience in containerized or distributed environments, while **maintaining flexibility** for advanced use cases.

```

gkoukis@Gkoukis:~/codeco-experiments$ ./install-cluster-ath-allinone.sh

Docker is installed, this is good.
jq tool is installed, this is good.
All input parameters are valid.
Deploying cluster number 21.

Enabling requested IM(s):
enable_xcpng_im is true
enable_vbox_im is false
enable_cloudlab_im is false
enable_aws_im is false

Disabled checking running status of DHCP, this is fine.
Check if docker image for XCP-NG IM is available locally.
Docker image swnuom/infrastructure-manager-xcpng is available.

Check if resource-manager image is available locally.
Docker image swnuom/resource-manager is available.

*** Generating docker-compose.yaml ***

*** Executing docker compose ***
[+] Running 7/7
  ✓ Network codeco-experiments_default                Created
  ✓ Volume "codeco-experiments_shared"                Created
  ✓ Volume "codeco-experiments_xcpng-im"              Created
  ✓ Container codeco-experiments-infrastructure-manager-xcpng-1 Created
  ✓ Container codeco-experiments-athw8-1              Created
  ✓ Container codeco-experiments-athm2-1              Created
  ✓ Container codeco-experiments-athw3-1              Created
Attaching to athm2-1, athw3-1, athw8-1, infrastructure-manager-xcpng-1
athw3-1 | creating ansible file for host.
athm2-1 | PLAY [athm2] *****
athm2-1 | TASK [installing helm] *****
athm2-1 | [WARNING]: Platform linux on host athm2 is using the discovered Python
athm2-1 | interpreter at /usr/bin/python3.10, but future installation of another Python
athm2-1 | interpreter could change the meaning of that path. See
athm2-1 | https://docs.ansible.com/ansible-
athm2-1 | core/2.16/reference_appendices/interpreter_discovery.html for more information.
athm2-1 | changed: [athm2]
athm2-1 | Task 'installing helm' SUCCESS. Duration: 0:00:17.683302
athm2-1 |
athm2-1 | PLAY RECAP *****
athm2-1 | athm2                : ok=1    changed=1    unreachable=0    failed=0    skipped=0
athm2-1 |
athm2-1 | Playbook execution complete.
athm2-1 | Task 'installing helm': SUCCESS - Duration: 0:00:17.683302
athm2-1 | The application helm has been installed and configured successfully.
athm2-1 |
athm2-1 | Triggered termination signal
infrastructure-manager-xcpng-1 | infrastructure-manager-xcpng-1 exited with code 0
athm2-1 exited with code 0

```

Figure 8: Snapshots of script execution and visualizer output.

3.3.3 Results Gathering and Reporting Phase

Once the experiments are completed, users can analyse the results and generate detailed reports. For this purpose, the `swnuom/output-results` Docker image is locally compiled and built using the [output results container.sh](#) script.

Key runtime metrics, such as deployment times for various tasks during cluster setup, are automatically saved in the [results/](#) directory. Post-deployment experimentation results are organized within subfolders named after the experiment, as specified by the user. This process leverages the [experiments_controller.sh](#) script and the metrics defined by the user in the [create_metrics.sh](#) script. Additional scripts, such as the [get_results_net.sh](#), are used to compute post-deployment statistics, including mean values and other aggregated metrics.

Users can also visualize their results through generated plots or create comprehensive reports. Reports can be produced as LaTeX-based PDF documents, which integrate visualizations and plots to present the experimental outcomes in a well-structured format.

3.3.4 Troubleshooting

CODEF includes mechanisms to assist users in identifying and resolving issues that may arise during installation or experimentation. In case the user's inputs are incorrect, missing, or if the prerequisites are not met, CODEF provides clear and informative error messages during the runtime. These messages are generated to assist in debugging by utilizing the [validate_input.sh](#) and the [valid-configurations.json](#) file as well as the Ansible visualizer. Note that users are required to fill this file with relevant details, specific to their deployment. This includes necessary information such as the names, IP addresses, and MAC addresses of the nodes to be deployed.

3.3.5 Customization

CODEF allows users to customize their experiments and deployment processes to address specific requirements, providing a high degree of flexibility and adaptability across diverse scenarios. Users can design and execute custom experiments, develop personalized scripts, and define targeted metrics for evaluation, leveraging CODEF's capabilities and abstraction layers with their unique needs and objectives.

To maintain compatibility across Linux systems and ensure broad usability without dependency on platform-specific software, CODEF leverages universal tools such as Bash scripting and Jq.

Its functionality can be extended for use in diverse environments by adopting the following approaches: **(i) leveraging already existing IM** to utilize pre-configured IMs (e.g., XCP-ng, VirtualBox, AWS) by copying the corresponding [configuration.ip](#) files and making necessary adjustments to the [configuration files](#); or **(ii) creating new IM**, by following the same methodology used for existing IMs. This involves creating a new image, copying the relevant files to the [containers/](#) directory (e.g., Dockerfiles and associated configurations), and integrating these with the [cluster_deployment.sh](#) script.

For automating the installation of specific software or applications, users can leverage the Resource Managers, developing custom playbooks tailored to their requirements. Subsequently, the updated [playbook](#) should be incorporated into the image by executing the [update_image.sh](#) scripts.

Finally, users must ensure that any new configurations or deployment parameters are added in the [valid-configurations.json](#) file.

3.4 Utilization and Integration with CODECO

As detailed in Section 3.2.2, CODEF enables the deployment of a wide range of applications and software through its Resource Manager, leveraging custom Ansible playbook templates. This capability allows CODEF to deploy the complete CODECO OSS, delivering fully functional cluster(s) with integrated CODECO components. For instance, the [install-acm-](#)

[cluster.sh](#) script facilitates this deployment process, following the instructions detailed in the [CODECO ACM repository](#). CODEF continues to be developed by partner ATH and is expected to **evaluate the global CODECO framework (OSS Basic Toolkit) in terms of performance and resource utilization under various conditions and loads.**

Beyond full-stack deployment, CODEF supports the deployment of some **standalone CODECO components**. Currently, it includes support for deploying **L2S-M** as a networking solution, as demonstrated by the [install-l2sm-cluster.sh](#) script. Initial assessments using CODEF have already been conducted to compare L2S-M with popular CNI plugins [2], showcasing its utility in evaluating and integrating CODECO-specific networking solutions.

CODEF is also **installed in the shared cloud space**, addressing the shared experimentation requirements of CODECO. This ensures that partners can efficiently collaborate within a unified framework while benefiting from shared infrastructure resources. Furthermore, CODEF's contributions align perfectly with KPI-related objectives (rf. to Section 4.1), enhancing the project's ability to meet performance benchmarks and deliver scalable, innovative solutions for CODECO's experimentation and deployment needs.

Additionally, as part of the relevant WP5 KPIs, CODEF **extends a multi-tenant mechanism** initially adopted during the EdgeNet installation process. This feature allows CODECO partners to contribute nodes and establish a CODECO ecosystem through CODEF, enabling teams to work and experiment, collaboratively. This capability is unique to CODEF, as it is typically absent from other initiatives (rf. to Section 2), or it requires proprietary or non-open-source solutions in order to achieve similar functionality.

4 Experimentation Methodology and Guidelines for Edge-Cloud Deployment

This section covers the guidelines and methodology aspects introduced in D10 and D15. Regarding the **experimentation guidelines**, CODECO builds upon the experimentation methodology first introduced in D10, with ACM benchmarking directives²⁴ serving as the foundation for the proposed guidelines. A benchmark consists of four essential components, namely: the quality to be benchmarked, the metrics quantifying the quality, the measurements methods, and the system status during measurement time (e.g., workload, usage profile, tasks). According to the defined KPIs and specific CODECO use cases, aspects of this methodological approach are expected to be **applied within the experimentation processes of WP5, while also leveraging CODEF**. Thus, the main purpose is to evaluate CODECO with respect to the CODECO KPIs which have been defined in the GA and which are again provided in Section 4.1.

The methodological approach in CODECO considers first the **collection of a set of potential measurements** and the corresponding **evaluation metrics**. Some indicative metrics are the pod readiness time, the pod removal time, the number of failed requests, the load balancer's overhead, measures on the distribution of requests, as well as networking-related metrics such as throughput, latency, RTT and packet loss. To this end, the consortium as agreed on a set of suitable metrics as detailed in D10, and which have been further refined for the use-cases in WP5.

Within the experimentation process, **baseline experiments** are initially performed, wherein nodes are in an "idle" state, i.e., running but not performing any cluster operations. This allows to measure latencies associated with create and delete operations or involve operations, such as restart, update. For example, to evaluate failure detection, re-start and recovery time system crashes are simulated by terminating containers abruptly, while users keep sending requests to obtain metrics, such as failed requests (e.g., based on chaos engineering tools). Certain operations of secondary importance, like image pulls, may be omitted through warm-up runs which ensure that images are already present on nodes upon experiment initialisation. In any case, delays should be considered between operations (e.g., via hard-coded waiting times) to achieve realistic conditions and allow the resources to settle down. Moreover, for more complex aspects such as scalability, the resource demand and load capacity metrics have been proposed, and can be evaluated by varying load and resources combinations to assess the system's ability to scale and handle demands, while maintaining satisfactory QoS. To this end, orchestration frameworks can be generated and tested with different numbers of nodes and workloads using tool to generate workload such as K-Bench²⁵.

Regarding **networking aspects**, tools such as iPerf(3)²⁶ and NetPerf²⁷ as well as cURL, and wget can be used for various aspects of networking, workload, and performance testing. In the context of K8s, NetPerf and iPerf(3) server/client can be created and deployed on the nodes of a K8s cluster to detect network properties, such as MTU size and bandwidth, while also measuring performance statistics, such as packet loss, delay, and jitter. cURL and wget can be used to directly access the K8s REST API, monitor the availability and web server responsiveness of applications deployed in K8s as well as monitor the services' health.

²⁴ <https://acmsigsoft.github.io/EmpiricalStandards/docs/?standard=Benchmarking>

²⁵ <https://github.com/vmware-tanzu/k-bench>

²⁶ <https://iperf.fr/>

²⁷ <https://github.com/HewlettPackard/netperf>

In the data plane, **stress scenarios** in which multiple pods/clusters are initiated in parallel to exhaust available resources are considered to assess the system's performance and resource utilization under heavy workloads. To evaluate networking aspects, both intra-node and inter-node communication are considered in related work with respect to both pod(s)-to-pod(s) and pod(s)-to-service(s) communication. Requests are exchanged among nodes e.g., in an all-to-all or in a one-to-all request mode, to create multiple routes.

Finally, **health-testing** can be utilized to assess the stability of the system, for example measuring the execution time of the health check, since the latter tends to grow, when the system gradually becomes underperforming, e.g., due to a high resource utilization. An interesting approach is to combine health check tools (e.g., active monitor²⁸) with checks based on Argo workflows²⁹ and utilize AD methods to predict reliability issues.

CODEF can support these mentioned aspects through its built-in or customizable measurement tools. By default, CODEF measures deployment times for each task during the installation and deployment phase and provides detailed monitoring and visualization of microservice-based systems using Jaeger. Additionally, its Resource Managers and custom Ansible playbooks enable the integration of third-party tools for extended analysis. CODEF can also incorporate chaos engineering and load testing tools, planned for use in the validation phase of various CODECO components and the complete OSS. Finally, via its IMs CODEF facilitates deployment across diverse heterogeneous environments, enabling the detection of potential performance differences, prerequisites and bottlenecks, thereby enhancing flexibility and adaptability.

Focusing on **security aspects** of K8s environments, guides/benchmarks such as the NSA/CISA K8s Hardening Guide or the CIS Kubernetes Benchmark³⁰ provide comprehensive set of practical recommendations and guidelines to enhance security and ensure compliance with industry best practices. They aim to secure native K8s components from security threats and vulnerabilities, including the API server, scheduler, etcd, etc. By integrating tools such as Kubescape³¹, kube-bench³² and OpenSCAP vulnerability scanning is automated across multiple frameworks. These tools, which are typically integrated into CI/CD pipelines, systematically check the compliance of Kubernetes clusters, highlighting the security status of different components and configurations. They also generate detailed reports that outline compliance levels (PASS or FAIL results) and provide step-by-step recommendations (remediation), facilitating continuous monitoring and proactive security management. In addition to the previous guides/benchmarks, open-source tools such as Trivy³³, Clair³⁴, Falco³⁵ or Kyverno³⁶ can be complementary employed to provide runtime security (e.g., real-time threat detection and monitoring) and policy management/enforcement capabilities. Thus, security features such as vulnerability checking and reporting can be integrated and utilized within the CODEF framework to further enhance resilience.

In these lines, **attack resilience** is also an aspect of particular interest. Security will be ensured by the ACM component and is expected to build upon the OCM Submariner tool³⁷ in the federated multi-clustering. Attack resilience will be evaluated against some widely known attack vectors (e.g., flooding, black-hole, or reverse attacks), by imitating sophisticated

²⁸ <https://github.com/keikoproj/active-monitor>

²⁹ <https://argoproj.github.io/argo-workflows/>

³⁰ <https://www.cisecurity.org/benchmark/kubernetes>

³¹ <https://kubescape.io/>

³² <https://github.com/aquasecurity/kube-bench>

³³ <https://trivy.dev/>

³⁴ <https://clairproject.org/>

³⁵ <https://falco.org/>

³⁶ <https://kyverno.io/>

³⁷ <https://submariner.io/>

attacker behaviour and assessing their impact on CODECO performance. Advanced attack detection methods will be assessed, including novel supervised and unsupervised AD techniques, with the involvement of the PDLC component.

In CODECO, we also aim to contribute to the state-of-the-art, by devising a **concrete methodology that fits the needs of multi-cluster solutions' benchmarking**. This process is currently under development within the ongoing efforts of WP4.

Furthermore, D15 introduced a **methodological framework for AI resilience and governance** within CODECO. Building on this, in the context monitoring and evaluation, a concrete methodology has been proposed, focusing on key concepts related to the applicability of ML/AI approaches in the ECI: **(i) Real-world and large-scale AI systems evaluation**, i.e., ensuring that AI systems are tested and validated under scenarios or conditions that closely replicate their operational environments, thereby enhancing their robustness and effectiveness; **(ii) Interplay between theoretical algorithmic properties and their impact on the edge-cloud resources**, i.e. evaluating the performance of AI algorithms in edge-cloud environments beyond traditional metrics (e.g., F1-score or recall) and incorporating system-level indicators, such as response time, memory usage, CPU utilization, latency and energy consumption; **(iii) Impact of heterogeneity, in terms of incorporated technologies and network specifications, in the performance of the ML/AI methods**, i.e., supporting experiments over heterogeneous physical and virtual resources through a common abstraction, considering an end-to-end view; **(iv) Resilience aspects**, i.e., enhancing cost efficiency, resource utilization and overall system resilience by applying ML and heuristic optimization techniques, AD algorithms and root cause analysis. These aspects can also be addressed and implemented using CODEF.

Aiming to evaluate AI/ML solutions in a declarative and automated manner, CODEF provides automation features that cover the entire experimental process (from the configuration up to the results visualization), which may significantly contribute towards intelligent and automated ML/AI evaluation in the entire AI lifecycle. Also, being based on a microservice architecture, CODEF is fully configurable and extensible, i.e., can be independently extended to accommodate additional ML/AI methods, as well as on-demand technologies, and features such as MLflow³⁸ and Kubeflow³⁹. Additionally, a proof-of-concept utilizing CODEF demonstrated its ability to effectively assess the performance of AD algorithms on real edge-cloud testbeds with promising results.

4.1 CODECO Framework KPIs

This section highlights the alignment of CODEF with CODECO objectives, particularly its role in WP5 experimentation as a key asset replacing EdgeNet for the *"Integration of the CODECO framework into the large-scale EdgeNet experimental infrastructure"*. CODEF closely aligns with these objectives and KPIs, contributing significantly to experimentation, scalability, use-case implementation and community engagement. Below is a summary of relevant to CODEF CODECO objectives, as well as a Table with the progress and verification measures. In this context, CODEF supports the achievement of related KPIs by:

- Enabling customizations based on CODECO application requirements and models.

³⁸ <https://mlflow.org/>

³⁹ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

- Conducting large-scale evaluations with diverse configurations, including cloud and edge deployments, CODECO assessments, and use-case scaling with additional containers and data sources.
- Assessing scalability aspects through experiments on large-scale platforms.
- Applying CODECO in operational environments and provide the experimentation framework to the research community.

Table 2: CODECO objectives and KPI reporting.

O1: To reduce the Edge-Cloud setup and management time via an automated, cognitive approach

O1 is first addressed in WP2, with the definition of the CODECO ecosystem and architecture, and then worked upon (concept, implementation and validation) in WP3, T3.1 and WP4, T4.1.

Experimentation and demonstration in WP5 (emulation framework, experimentation, demos, A5, A6, A7) will lead to specific customization, derived from CODECO application requirements and models (WP2, WP5, WP6, WP7; A2, A3).

Progress M1-18 and Verification Measures:

- CODECO architecture definition in WP2 ([D10](#))
- CODECO OSS Toolkit, WP3 ([D12](#), [code](#))
- Initial experimentation ([publications in Zenodo](#))

KPIs:

KPI1.1: Time taken to setup and configure multiple services based on 1 cluster across Edge-Cloud; **Assessment:** Measurements for 1 service, involving 5 Edges to Cloud deployments (M18); 10-20 services across 20 Edge-Cloud deployments (M24); 50-100 services; across 50 Edge-Cloud deployments (M36)

KPI1.2: Percentage of manual intervention required against Kubernetes when setting up a cluster across Edge-Cloud; **Assessment** - Measurements for 1 service, involving 5 Edges to Cloud (M18); 10-20 services across 20 Edge-Cloud deployments (M24); 50-100 services across 50 Edge-Cloud deployments (M36)

KPI1.1 (M18). *Partially achieved.* Measurements done in P5 (1 cluster, 2 worker nodes) show lower latency for CODECO than plain K8s.

KPI1.2 (M18). *Delayed.*

O2: To optimize Edge-Cloud operations via a privacy preserving data-compute-network orchestration

During service runtime, the CODECO cognitive framework shall provide a unique approach to the optimization and personalization of the overall Edge-Cloud operation by addressing management and orchestration based on a holistic data-network-compute approach (KIPs1-5). During runtime, CODECO shall actively check potential triggers for changes (PDLc), e.g., for workload migration, for specific infrastructure adaptation, and for data management (KIP6). This objective is addressed in WP3 (CODECO basic operation and toolkit, A5, A3) and WP5 (A4).

Progress M1-18 and Verification Measures:

- CODECO experimentation framework has been set (WP5)
- EdgeNet experimentation proposal has been created (WP5)
- CODECO shared Cloud infrastructure has been set (consortium) (WP5)
- Initial experimentation has been developed based on specific components, e.g., ACM, SWM and NetMA (partially)

KPI2.1: *Accuracy.* Assessment: Experimentation in EdgeNet and labs (M12, M24); large-scale evaluation derived from variability e.g., adding new nodes; increasing mobility in the participants in the system (M36).

KPI2.2: *Latency.* Measurements against a Cloud-based approach for 1 application, an Edge-Cloud based on 2 containers (M12); Use-cases dimensioning, involving at least 3 containers on the Edge and 1 on the Cloud (M24, M36), and 10 data sources; explore the increase in latency against the increase in data sources, containers on Cloud-Edge (M36).

KPI2.1 (M12) achieved – rf. to [CODECO Deliverable D22](#) for a list of scientific publications covering experimentation aspects.

KPI2.2 (M12): Achieved, based on use-case P5.

O3: To provide automated, privacy preserving and secure management of multi-cluster, multi-domain environments

The CODECO components provide support for automated behavior (during Edge-Cloud setup and runtime) assuming Edges that are limited to 1 domain (single cluster operation, WP3) or Edge-Cloud environments and services running across multiple domains (multi-domain, multi-cluster operation, WP4). This objective and the revision of KPIs is performed in WP2, while the concept development, integration and validation is then addressed in WP4. In WP5, aspects concerning scalability shall be evaluated, and customizations may be derived thereof. O3 is integrated into assets A1, A2, A3 and A6.

Progress M1-18 and Verification Measures:

Not applicable.

KPI3.1: *Time to setup CODECO in federated clusters.* Assessment: Measurements involving 3 clusters (M24); 10 clusters (M36); Extrapolation derived from experiments in a large-scale platform (e.g., EdgeNet) (M36)

KPI3.2: *Level of manual intervention.* Assessment: Measurements involving 2 clusters (M24); 10 clusters (M30); 50 clusters (M36); extrapolation derived from experiments in large-scale platforms such as EdgeNet (M36).

Not applicable in M1-M18

O4: To support multi-domain Edge Cloud operations integrating openness and greenness

The CODECO framework shall be deployed in different phases and offered during the project runtime as open-source Software (WP7). The definition of the modular architecture is performed in WP2. Then, the different modules of CODECO shall be provided regularly in stable releases (WP3, WP4). In WP5 CODECO shall be applied to specific operational environments in use-cases. CODECO shall also have as result an experimentation framework, currently envisioned to be made available to the research community via EdgeNet (WP5, WP6). Relates to all KIPs and is observable in assets A1-A7.

Progress M1-18 and Verification Measures:

- Early release of the OSS basic toolkit in Oct 2023 (WP3)
- OSS toolkit release in June 2023 (WP3)
- Initial deployment of CODECO in use-cases (WP5)

KPI4.1: deployment in realistic infrastructures. Assessment: Each use-case integrating at least 10 CODECO nodes across 1 cluster (M18); across at least 3 clusters (M36).

KPI4.2: Number of external entities deploying CODECO. Assessment: Measurement in events: at least 20 (M18); at least 50 (M36).

KPI4.3: Number of developers interested in CODECO. Assessment: At least 20 (M18); at least 50 (M36).

KPI4.1 (M18): use-cases consider 1 cluster, not necessarily yet with 10 nodes.

KPI4.2 (M18) Achieved – rf. to [Deliverable D22](#) and to the [CODECO Eclipse GitLab repositories](#)

KPI4.3 (M18): achieved – rf. to [Deliverable D22](#).

O5: To build a consolidated ecosystem appealing to the different CODECO stakeholder groups

CODECO plans to raise awareness to its mechanisms both via broad dissemination and scientific outreach (WP6); via its different use-cases and the integration in EdgeNet (WP5), as well as via the establishment of liaisons to relevant standardisation entities and relevant fora (WP6) and to concrete exploitation actions, including the IRCEP (WP7). Additionally, the integration of CODECO in large-scale experimental efforts as detailed in section 1.3.3 and WP3, WP4, WP5 shall assist in reaching broader impact in the scientific community as well. Initial plans to further strengthen the impact of CODECO towards standardisation are described in section 2.2.2 and WP6, T6.3. Relates with all KIPs and is based on the use-cases (WP5) and CODECO assets. Relates also with all assets A1-A7.

Progress M1-18 and Verification Measures:

- List of events and respective reports.
- Involvement in *Standards Development Organisations (SDO)* (T6.3), related fora (e.g., [AIOTI](#), [EUCEI](#)).

KPI5.1: Number of liaisons to stakeholder groups. **Assessment:** At least 5 (M12); at least 10 (M18); At least 20 (M36)

KPI5.1 (M18): achieved

KPI5.2 (M18): achieved (via events)

KPI5.2: Number of entities interested in CODECO. **Assessment:** At least 10 (M18); At least 20 (M36).

KPI5.3: Number of integrated nodes in EdgeNet. **Assessment:** At least 1 (M18); at least 5 (M36)

KPI5.4: Number of entities addressed in IRCEP. **Assessment:** At least 20 (M18); At least 50 (M36).

KPI5.5: Number of entities using CODECO after IRCEP. **Assessment:** At least 5 (M18); At least 20 (M36).

KPI5.3 (M18): achieved, partners ATH and FOR.

KPI5.4 (M18): achieved.

KPI5.5 (M18): achieved

5 CODECO Framework Evaluation Plan

This section details the evaluation plan for the CODECO framework, including its deployment, verification and validation workflows. It describes the steps for leveraging GitLab to manage issues, track progress, and validate solutions collaboratively.

To ensure a standardized approach for evaluating the CODECO framework across different CODECO partners, an extensive use of the [CODECO GitLab](#) platform has been adopted. This enables consistent tracking of issues and documentation of solutions or changes applied. The following subsections describe the procedure for deploying the CODECO framework, along with the corresponding verification process, to identify and address issues during the evaluation.

5.1 Deployment of CODECO in KinD and non-KinD environments

This section provides a step-by-step guide to deploy and use CODECO OSS. While CODECO is designed to operate in any K8s environment, at this stage of the project, deployment on a KinD cluster is recommended using the [kind-config.yaml](#) file. This configuration file has been created to set up the cluster for all CODECO components via the ACM component. The installation has been tested on a 3-node KinD cluster running on an Ubuntu 20.04 machine.

CODECO is also being tested in non-KinD environments, across various infrastructures and architectures (e.g., arch64) and K8s distributions such as vanilla K8s, and MicroK8s. This testing process is ongoing. From the CODEF perspective, since VMs are created from scratch during each cluster installation across different infrastructures via the IMs, aspects of the installation are expected to be adapted for compatibility. A brief overview of the steps required to deploy and use CODECO OSS is provided below. For detailed instructions, please refer to the [CODECO ACM repository](#).

Step 1: Installation of software prerequisites

- Basic apt dependencies, yq, Docker (and standard post-installation steps), KinD, Helm, Golang and kubectl.

Step 2: Cluster Creation

- Clone the ACM repository.
- Create a local KinD cluster using the [kind-config.yaml](#) configuration file that meets the CODECO requirements.

Step 3: Installation of the CODECO Framework

- Export Dockerhub credentials.
- Deploy CODECO components i.e., ACM automatically deploys all CODECO components with the [post_deploy.sh](#) script.
 - Build a custom Docker image or use a pre-built one.

Step 4: Deploy a sample CODECO App

- Consists of a frontend and backend as described in [codeco v1alpha1 codecoapp ver3.yaml](#).

The successful deployment of the CODECO framework results in the output of all running pods, as illustrated in Figure 9.

NAMESPACE	NAME	READY	STATUS	RESTARTS	AGE
cert-manager	cert-manager-655ff476d-zxn2f	1/1	Running	0	26m
cert-manager	cert-manager-cainjector-6654f55cb7-1j6n8	1/1	Running	0	26m
cert-manager	cert-manager-webhook-6db4d44ff-7rggz	1/1	Running	0	26m
default	netperf-host-r5vb7	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-host-tw1jd	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-host-z9vp5	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-7bb86f5cbf-2f97s	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-7bb86f5cbf-vgh94	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-f5bg5	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-fn8dr	1/1	Running	0	18m
default	netperf-pod-gd62m	1/1	Running	0	18m
he-codeco-acm	acm-operator-controller-manager-75568d6b7d-phbv1	2/2	Running	0	27m
he-codeco-acm	acm-swm-app-backend	1/1	Running	0	2m25s
he-codeco-acm	acm-swm-app-front-end	1/1	Running	0	2m25s
he-codeco-mdm	freshness-connector-check-connection-75d498fc7d-9lpdp	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	k8s-connector-check-connection-5b9446648d-k7sh2	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	kubescape-connector-check-connection-78c56795cb-vmzt8	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-api-0	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-controller-0	1/1	Running	3 (12m ago)	15m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-kafka-0	1/1	Running	0	17m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-neo4j-0	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-mdm	mdm-zookeeper-0	1/1	Running	0	17m
he-codeco-netma	c1-lpm-88b7ff96d-9sx5n	1/1	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-netma	c2-lpm-7478546bc8-6n58q	1/1	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-netma	kind-control-plane-lpm-67db47c77f-h7gc6	1/1	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-controller-7df785c975-xkwdb	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-controller-manager-5c7b4646bf-q6fqs	2/2	Running	1 (22m ago)	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-operator-7748d55c4d-qkxxw	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-switch-4m84g	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-switch-9p8d7	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	l2sm-switch-k8cgh	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	mysql-pod	1/1	Running	0	23m
he-codeco-netma	nemesis-5d88bbfc55-xf8xb	1/1	Running	0	18m
he-codeco-netma	prometheus-lpm-network-7f6dcf54f8-fgxb9	2/2	Running	0	19m
he-codeco-pdlc	gnn-controller-5f54d96856-svtcv	1/1	Running	0	11m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-ca-56ddfd975-8ws4c	1/1	Running	0	12m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-dp-57756f8f66-f8v6d	1/1	Running	0	15m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-gnn-inference-596f5b9cc-pw9s2	1/1	Running	0	11m
he-codeco-pdlc	pdlc-rl-796559d96-z7q7d	1/1	Running	0	7m46s
he-codeco-swm	controller-manager-687478449d-6lxlx	2/2	Running	0	5m50s
he-codeco-swm	solver-6f8f47857f-9r68k	1/1	Running	0	5m50s
kepler	kepler-exporter-5w6ks	1/1	Running	0	2m31s
kepler	kepler-exporter-mb88q	1/1	Running	0	2m31s
kepler	kepler-exporter-pkhh8	1/1	Running	0	2m31s

Figure 9: Pod output after CODECO installation in KinD.

The option to deploy the entire CODECO framework within a Docker container is also available. This approach is ideal for users who wish to install CODECO in a protected and reversible environment, provided Docker is already installed on their system. The GitLab profile repository of CODECO includes the following resources:

- A Readme file.
- A [Dockerfile-integration](#) file, that builds a container image with all software prerequisites.
- An [integration-script.sh](#) script, which runs all installation steps within the container.
- A [create-kind-cluster.sh](#) script, which creates a KinD cluster with 3 nodes and installs some necessary plugins.

5.2 Verification of CODECO

In this section, the procedure to GitLab strategy to test CODECO is explained by using an activity diagram (Figure 10). Assuming the installation of CODECO and the CODECO App is complete, the user can proceed with the verification process. The following aspects can be validated:

Verify Correct Deployment of CODECO

- An [integration-test.sh](#) script, which verifies the correct CODECO installation and functionality.

Verify CODECO functionality:

- Retrieve the CRs to check if the `errmsg` field (visible only after the operator processes the resource) has been updated. This change confirms that CODECO successfully deployed the application.
- Test NetMA Component Metrics.
- Test that PDLC correctly provides `nodeRecommendations` to SWM.

Check application deployment

- The sample application deployment generates two additional pods: a Front-End Pod and a Back-End Pod.
- After deploying the sample application, the status of these new pods is checked to confirm successful deployment.

Figure 10: Activity diagram – test and deployment of the CODECO infrastructure and application deployment.

5.3 Issues Tracking and Validation Workflow in CODECO GitLab

A complex system like CODECO employs various methods to automate its internal processes and deployment across diverse environments. Thanks to the involvement of CODECO

partners and the six distinct use cases, CODECO has been successfully deployed in both bare-metal and virtual environments. However, each environment introduces unique configurations that can occasionally lead to challenges, particularly during installation, and in some rare cases, affect its internal functionalities.

To ensure the CODECO framework is accessible to everyone and functional across diverse setups, the [CODECO GitLab](#) was utilized to create, track and resolve issues found by different partners or even the general public. Figure 11 presents a high-level diagram of the tracking and validation workflow, which involves two key actors: the *Issue Opener* and the *Developer*. The former is responsible for opening an issue found on the installation or usage of CODECO, providing information to the developers as well as and validating proposed solutions to confirm their effectiveness before closing the issue. The *Developer* assigns the appropriate partner to address the issue, requests additional details, develops solutions, opens related issues if necessary and ultimately closes an issue once the solution is verified.

The following subsections, provide a more detailed and lower-level explanation of the processes depicted in Figure 11. Section 5.3.1 describes the “Issue Creation” and “Find Appropriate Assignee” activities. Section 5.3.2 corresponds to the “Request Information”, “Provide Information”, “Create a Solution” and “Open Related Issues (Issue Creation)” activities. Lastly, Section 5.3.4 describes the validation and closure process of the activities “Validate Solution”, “Verify Solution” and “Issue Closure”.

Figure 11: GitLab high-level tracking and validation workflow.

5.3.1 Issues Creation and Documentation

The *Issue Opener* actor, as previously mentioned, is responsible of creating a new issue on CODECO's GitLab. This actor may be a member of the CODECO consortium, such as a developer or use-case member, or the general public. To open an issue, the *Issue Opener* provides a detailed description along with any relevant logs in one of the CODECO GitLab projects. Additionally, tags are used to offer developers a clear and concise categorization and explanation of the issue.

The "Find Appropriate Assignee" activity commences upon the creation of an issue. The leaders of CODECO's Task4.4 – Open Federated Edge-Cloud Toolkit Development (ICOM) are tasked with reviewing and updating issue tags, adding any necessary information, and reassigning the issue to the appropriate partner. Once reassigned, the receiving partner manages the "Find Appropriate Assignee" process within their developer team, ensuring the issue is allocated to the correct project and member of the CODECO consortium. This process follows a top-down approach, streamlining the identification of the right assignee and accelerating issue resolution. Additionally, if an issue blocks the workflow of another, the two issues are linked, providing clarity on the dependency and aiding in prioritizing resolution.

5.3.2 Management workflow of Issue Resolution

Once the appropriate *Developer* is assigned to an open issue, it is possible to request more information from the *Issue Opener*. This is initiated through the “Request Information” activity, which triggers the “Provide Information” of the *Issue Opener*. These two activities can be triggered multiple times, until the *Developer* has gathered sufficient information from the *Issue Opener* to address the issue.

After acquiring the required information, the *Developer* is able to: (i) Create the solution, as shown by the “Create a Solution” activity and (ii) Open more related issues, as shown by the “Open Related Issues (Issue Creation)” activity. Here, the Developer provides a clear and detailed explanation of the solution, enabling the Issue Opener to validate the fix by triggering the “Validate Solution” activity. By opening more related issues, the *Developer* is triggering again the “Issue Creation” activity, acting as the *Issue Opener* actor for the new issues. As described in Section 5.3.1, the new issue is linked to the current issue through GitLab relationships.

5.3.3 Validation and Closure of Identified Issues

Once a solution is provided by the Developer, the “Validate Solution” activity is triggered. This activity can result in either success or failure. If the solution is successfully validated, the *Issue Opener* verifies the solution and then the *Developer* proceeds on closing the current issue. In case of a failure on the validation process from the *Issue Opener*, the “Provide Information” activity is triggered, detailing the reasons for the failure and providing additional feedback to the Developer.

By following the above guidelines, the tracking and validation workflow of each issue can be resolved, offering a clear representation of its status. This process provides CODECO developers with valuable insights into the workload required to address identified issues and resolve any problems related to CODECO's installation or internal functionality. Figure 12 illustrates the Issue Analytics in the ECL GitLab, showcasing the number of issues tracked and managed within the platform.

Figure 12: Issue analytics in ECL GitLab.

6 CODECO Experimentation Environments

This section covers the experimentation facilities utilized for the deployment and validation of CODECO including shared resources via the AWS cloud infrastructure and the UC partners testbeds and equipment.

6.1 CODECO Shared Cloud Infrastructure

IBM makes available to the consortium cloud resources on a dedicated account on AWS, the largest cloud provider in existence today. The costs of the resources on that cloud account are paid for by SERI (State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, a founding body of the Swiss Federal Government) through a grant to IBM Research GmbH in the context of the Horizon Europe agreements between Switzerland and the European Union.

IBM is the only partner with access to the management console and is responsible for the provision of resources and management of costs on the cloud account. Partners may have access to resources provisioned in the account either through:

- AWS credentials with limited permissions for the operation of the resources/services using IAM (Identity Access Management), or
- Credentials on the resources as configured by the partners making use of them, such as SSH keys to access VM, for example.

Services accessed through IAM may be available from the Internet as any other AWS service. Resources backed by general-purpose computing devices such as virtual machines are protected behind a firewall that may only be accessed through the use of a Virtual Private Network (VPN) client. We are using Tailscale²² as the provider of the VPN services to the resources on the AWS account for both IBM and participating partners.

The Tailscale client allows end-user devices, such as laptops, and gateways in on-premises infrastructure or edge devices, access to the resources on cloud. A management console is used by IBM to grant access to devices from registered users, and to partition, where and when necessary, which partners have access to which resources on cloud. For example, some partners may only be interested in accessing a subset of the VMs for their experimentation/development purposes, while others in charge of deploying and maintaining infrastructure may be granted access to all VMs.

6.1.1 Integration cluster

The integration cluster consists of a single K8s node dedicated to supporting integration activities. The node in the cluster is provisioned to support high-performance integration tasks, ensuring that the hardware requirements of CODECO components can be fulfilled, featuring Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS as the Operating System, 2 x Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4214 CPUs @ 2.20GHz, 128GB Memory (RAM) and 3 x 960GB and RAID 5 hard drives. GitLab Runners have been set up by partner ICOM in the [official CODECO Eclipse Repository](#), which is made open source and open to the community. Runners running at integration testbed K8s cluster provided by ICOM, take charge of executing the CI/CD pipelines (described in the [gitlab-ci.yml](#) file), to automate the procedures of testing, building, packaging and deployment. For the resource monitoring of the cluster, K8s Dashboard, Prometheus and Grafana, are configured and utilized, providing valuable insights on the health status of each CODECO component.

Here it is important to note that the integration of CODECO components and OSS is primarily carried out in the on-premises environments of project partners to ensure compatibility (rf. to Section 6.2).

6.1.2 Experimentation Cluster

The experimentation cluster consists of nine nodes dedicated to supporting experimentation activities. Each node in the cluster is designed to support demanding experimentation tasks, featuring high-performance Intel Xeon CPUs with 16 threads, 64 GB of DDR4 RAM, and NVMe SSD storage. The nodes also offer full virtualization support and robust memory and disk resources for diverse workloads. The cluster is fully operational, with CODEF successfully installed within the AWS environment via its AWS IM. Partners with access can utilize the cluster either by leveraging CODEF for their experiments or by directly accessing the nodes to conduct their experiments independently, provided they have the necessary credentials.

To manage resource allocation effectively, ATH has developed an Excel file for node reservation and scheduling. This includes an availability calendar that is refreshed weekly and a request form for partners to “book” nodes for a specified duration, ensuring fair and efficient access to resources for those with access rights and fostering collaborative use of the shared infrastructure.

The figure displays three screenshots of an Excel spreadsheet used for node reservation and scheduling. Each screenshot shows a different tab of the spreadsheet.

Availability Calendar Tab: This tab shows the status of nodes in the experimentation cluster. The columns represent nodes, and the rows represent dates. The status of each node is indicated by a color: yellow for 'In Use' and green for 'Free'. The date shown is 16/12/2024.

Update Date	ip-XXX								
16/12/2024	In Use	In Use	In Use	Free	Free	Free	Free	Free	Free

Request Form with Descriptions Tab: This tab shows a table of requested experiments. The columns include Date of Request, Experiment ID, Partner Name, Number of Nodes Requested, Nodes ID, Requested Start Date, Requested End Date, Duration (in days), Short Experiment Description, and Status.

Date of Request	Experiment ID	Partner Name	Number of Nodes Requested	Nodes ID	Requested Start Date	Requested End Date	Duration (in days)	Short Experiment Description (what is the Experiment's Target and which CODECO aspects are tested)	Status (Waiting, Allocated, Completed)
18/11/2024	ATH1	George Koukis (ATH)	3	ip-XXX, ip-XXX, ip-XXX	4/11/2024	18/11/2024	14	Testing CODECO Framework deployment with CODEF	Allocated

Historical Allocations Tab: This tab shows a table of completed experiments. The columns include Experiment ID, Partner Name, Number of Nodes Requested, Requested Start Date, Requested End Date, Duration (in days), Status, Experiment Outcome, and Code / URL.

Experiment ID	Partner Name	Number of Nodes Requested	Requested Start Date	Requested End Date	Duration (in days)	Status	Experiment Outcome	Code / URL
ATH1	George Koukis (ATH)	3	9/11/2024	9/12/2024	14	Completed	CODEF integration to Shared Cloud	

Figure 13: Excel tabs for node reservation and scheduling.

At this stage of the project, the utilization of the shared cloud cluster is still in its early phases. However, its role in supporting multi-cluster and federated experimentation, as emphasized in WP4, highlights its importance. Thus, the cluster provides a scalable and flexible platform for diverse experimentation scenarios, aligning with CODECO's overarching objectives.

6.2 Lab Experimentation

The deployment environments provided by CODECO partners are designed to support the application of CODECO in six specific use-cases, enabling performance evaluation within these experimental settings. The CODECO use-cases (or pilots) are the following:

- Smart Monitoring of Public Infrastructure (P1), led by the University of Göttingen (UGOE) and the City of Göttingen.
- Vehicular Digital Twin for Safe Urban Mobility (P2), led by i2CAT Foundation (i2CAT).
- MDS Across Decentralized Edge-Cloud (P3), led by Telefónica Innovación Digital (TID).
- Demand-Side Management in Decentralized Grids (P4), led by the Polytechnic University of Madrid (UPM).
- Wireless AGV Control for Flexible Factories (P5), led by fortiss (FOR).
- Smart Buildings (P6), led by Almende (ALM).

These use-cases will be deployed as a foundation for experimentation and demonstrations in real operational environments. A brief overview of the infrastructures utilized is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Infrastructure details of use cases.

Use Cases	Description
P1	A controlled environment with 2-3 CODECO nodes (LiDAR sensors and NVIDIA Jetson Xavier edge devices) deployed in a small-scale testbed. In later stages, 5-6 more traffic areas will be utilized to deploy the same setup.
P2	Three nodes with different computational capabilities: an NVIDIA Jetson Orin, an NVIDIA Jetson Orin Nano, and a Supermicro SYS-610C-TR rackable server.
P3	Three virtual Linux nodes.
P4	One building with energy monitoring nodes installed. IoT sensors collect real-time energy consumption data from general utilities (HVAC, lighting) and specialized energy assets (PV panels, battery systems). In later stages of the project more buildings will be utilized.
P5	One Controller (K8s master node) and eight worker nodes. The Controller node has been deployed in a Lenovo ThinkPad X280 laptop, and eight worker nodes involve two TurtleBot3 MARs and six Raspberry Pi 4 devices.
P6	One Server, two Hubs, six Crownstones and three Sensors.

7 Evaluation with CODEF

In this section, we present some proof-of-concept results that demonstrate CODEF's capabilities for rapid, reliable and reproducible experimentation of Kubernetes-based edge cloud deployments, under a diverse range of experimental objectives and requirements, and various deployment alternatives. In particular, the evaluation analysis demonstrates the supported automated experiments on various research topics, e.g., from network plugin to AD workflows performance assessments, the integration with external edge environments and testbeds e.g. EdgeNet.

Our analysis is based on the following concrete experimental scenarios, previously published in [5]-[8]:

- **Scenario 1** - Evaluation of various network fabrics across different (standard and edge-oriented) K8s distributions.
- **Scenario 2** - Comparative analysis of a diverse set of networking mechanisms/tools across different lightweight K8s distributions with regards to their performance and resource utilization.
- **Scenario 3** - Automated deployment of EdgeNet and features.
- **Scenario 4** - Assessment of anomaly detection (AD) workflows tailored for edge environments.

We explore the four aforementioned scenarios across two testbeds, located at the ATHENA Research Center (ATH) and the University of Macedonia (UoM), showcasing the use of CODEF for heterogeneous installations across diverse infrastructures. Both testbeds use the XCP-ng virtualization platform, and thus the XCP IM of CODEF. The former testbed consists of a single Dell PowerEdge T640 physical machine equipped with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4210R processor running at 2.40GHz, a 16-core CPU and 64GB RAM. The latter comprises two Dell PowerEdge R630 physical servers, each one with 2 Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2620 v4 processors operating at 2.10GHz with 16-core CPUs.

Scenario 1 - Evaluation of various network fabrics across different Kubernetes distributions.

CODEF supports a variety of K8s distributions and network plugins ranging from resource-intensive, production-based and feature-rich solutions to more lightweight and resource-constrained approaches. In this context, CODEF may serve as an experimental platform for the performance evaluation of various network fabrics across different edge-oriented Kubernetes distributions and vice-versa, offering major insights regarding their suitability and applicability in a diverse set of edge-cloud use-cases.

In this scenario, we assess 5 representative CNI plugins across 4 distributions (3 lightweight and vanilla K8s) over two distinct testbeds (ATH and UoM). In particular, we consider the Flannel, Calico, Cilium, Kube-router and Kube-ovn CNI plugins, and the vanilla K8s, K3s, K0s and MicroK8s distributions.

The evaluation metrics include the **CPU and RAM utilization**, and the **throughput** gains of the compared CNI plugins across resource-restricted environments and various connectivity conditions. We focus on the pod-to-pod (p2p), communication for both **TCP and UDP protocols**. Furthermore, we consider intra-host and inter-host communication scenarios, where hosts are located either on the same or on different machines. Finally, we analyse the **pod startup latency**, for various plugins and distributions as the number of pods scales in an intra-host communication scenario.

Regarding the experimentation methodology, the installation of the K8s distributions and the respective plugins (based on their most recent stable versions), is carried out in a cluster comprising one master and two worker nodes (VMs). We assess each plugin in terms of CPU, RAM and throughput; the aforementioned metrics are obtained through the Kubernetes Network Benchmark (KNB) tool. KNB deploys sets of client/server pods using a packaged iperf3 tool to measure the networking performance and resource usage. Results are based on 10 iterations, after each iteration the cluster is deleted and then re-deployed to ensure the reliability of results.

Figure 14: CPU, RAM usage and throughput per CNI plugin, for different K8s distributions (ATH testbed).

Figure 14 depicts the resource consumption and the throughput performance of the CNI plugins across the considered K8s distributions, with regards to the **intra-host communication scenario** (ATH testbed). Focusing on the CPU usage (Figure 14a and 14d), the selection of K8s distribution does not significantly impact the plugins' CPU utilization, except from Calico, for TCP communication and K0s and Mk8s implementations, due to a shift from underlay to overlay mechanisms. Flannel and Cilium are less CPU intensive, while Calico, Kube-ovn and Kube-router show a higher CPU consumption. Furthermore, we notice that UDP scenarios (Figure 14d) are characterized by an increased CPU consumption for all considered plugins, compared to TCP communication due to the higher packet rate and continuous system-call operations. These outcomes are in line with the recent literature [11].

On the other hand, the RAM consumption of the employed plugins heavily depends on the K8s distribution, as shown in Figures 14b and 14e. For example, Flannel efficiently reduces its RAM utilization for both K3s and Mk8s, resulting in the lowest RAM consumption among the employed plugins. Interestingly, Kube-ovn and Cilium provide increased RAM consumption when deployed over lightweight K8s distributions, i.e., Mk8s and K3s, indicating that **the selection of a lightweight K8s distribution does not always ensure a lower resource consumption for the plugins**. Moreover, the reduced RAM usage of Calico for the K0s and Mk8s distributions aligns with the results of CPU utilization. We note that the selection UDP or TCP does not affect the RAM consumption of the considered plugins.

Finally, Figures 14c and 14f illustrates the throughput performance. In the TCP-related conditions, the pure IP-based leading plugins, i.e., Calico and Kube-router, achieve throughput performances that exceed 9000 Mbps, whereas the remaining plugins consistently fall at 1000 Mbps. An exception is identified for Calico (in K0s and MicroK8s), where the **reduction in resource consumption comes at the cost of decreased throughput**. On the other hand, UDP-based communications exhibit lower performance near 1000 Mbps for all plugins and distributions.

Figure 15: CPU, RAM usage and throughput per CNI plugin, for different K8s distributions (UoM testbed).

In Figure 15, we investigate the performance of the deployed plugins in the **inter-host communication scenario** (UoM testbed). Regarding the CPU usage across K8s distributions (Figures 15a and 15d, the results are aligned with those observed in the intra-host scenario, although there are differences in the actual CPU values due to the hardware variations of the two testbeds. Flannel again outperforms the rest of the plugins in terms of CPU consumption, while Kube-ovn is the most CPU-intensive. In terms of RAM usage (Figure 15b and 15e), the results also reveal similar patterns to these of the intra-host scenario. Finally, the throughput performance of the plugins is shown in Figures 15c and 15f. As expected, the inter-host scenario presents decreased throughput performance as no plugin exceeds the 1000 Mbps threshold. Moreover, **plugins based on underlay IP routing**, i.e., Calico and Kube-router, **surpass the performance of VXLAN overlay-based** ones, i.e., Flannel and Cilium. In this context, Kube-router exhibits higher and more consistent throughput performance for UDP/TCP protocols.

Figure 16: Average pod readiness time for different plugins and distributions with varying numbers of pods (ATH testbed).

Finally, we present the results of the readiness time experiment. Here, the results of the Mk8s distribution are excluded due to significant variations in readiness times and abnormal system crashes when deploying more than 50 pods. The pods are deployed using a minimal pause container image to focus solely on K8s' scheduling and network setup. For each test run, pods are deployed in batches of increasing sizes (from 1 to 100) to gain insights into how system performance scales under different loads.

Figure 16 demonstrates the average pod startup latency across the selected CNI plugins and K8s flavours as the number of pods increases. The deployment of a single pod requires approximately 1 to 1.5 seconds across all evaluated platforms, whereas the readiness time for 100 pods may extend up to 30 seconds in the case of vanilla K8s. Focusing on readiness times among plugins, the results vary based on the pod count. Notably, Kube-ovn outperforms the other K8s solutions, showcasing the lowest increment in latency as the number of pods increases. In contrast, Cilium consistently exhibits slower readiness times throughout our experimental evaluation. An interesting observation is Kube-router, which initially performs well; however, its performance significantly declines as the pod count exceeds 40, highlighting the significance of networking plugins in scalability scenarios. Moreover, when deployed within **lighter K8s distributions** such as K0s and K3s, all plugins **show enhanced performance relative to their vanilla K8s counterparts**. For instance, K3s and K0s with Calico exhibit readiness times that are up to 7 and 12 seconds faster, respectively, for clusters of 60 and 100 pods compared to vanilla K8s. These results, combined with the low resource requirements, underscore the benefits of lightweight distributions, especially in scenarios with increasing load.

Scenario 2 – Assessment of networking mechanisms/tools across lightweight K8s distributions.

In this subsection we extend the evaluation analysis of Scenario 1, focusing on the impact of key CNI plugins features, such as **tunnelling**, **security** and **service mesh/observability options**, within various CNI networking solution across resource-intensive and lightweight K8s distributions. The evaluation metrics include the **CPU and RAM consumption**, along with the **throughput** performance, provided from the p2p communication for both the **TCP and UDP protocols**. In particular, we evaluate the performance of major features provided by 5 different

CNI plugins, i.e., Antrea, Calico, Cilium, Flannel and Kube-ovn, over 2 representative K8s distributions, i.e., the common vanilla K8s and a lightweight K8s flavour, MicroK8s (MK8s). The features under investigation are categorized as follows: i) Tunnelling: VXLAN, IPIP, GEN and NoEncapsulation or HostGW; ii) Security & Encryption: WG, IPsec, eBPF and Istio; iii) Service mesh and Monitoring/Visualization: Istio, Linkerd and Observability (i.e., Prometheus and Grafana).

Regarding the experimentation methodology, the considered CNI plugins were implemented utilizing the CODEF. Each CNI plugin is deployed on the appropriate K8s distribution (vanilla or edge-oriented Mk8s), and experiments are executed over the ATH experimentation testbed. Results are assessed for 10 iterations using the KNB tool with 15 minutes of sleep time for CPU cooling between the run times. After each experiment the cluster, consisting of 1 master and 2 worker nodes, is destroyed and then redeployed with a different plugin to ensure no remnants of previous experiments exist.

Figure 17: Tunnelling options of vanilla K8s plugins for CPU, RAM usage and throughput - p2p TCP scenario.

Figure 18: Tunnelling options of vanilla K8s plugins for CPU, RAM usage and throughput - p2p UDP scenario.

Tunnelling scenario: Figure 17 illustrates the throughput and resource utilization (CPU and RAM) of the CNI plugins over the Vanilla K8s distribution for TCP communication, regarding the tunnelling protocols. The results demonstrate the improved throughput performance of Calico for all investigated tunnelling options, which, however, comes at the cost of increased RAM and CPU consumption, i.e. 700 MB and 25%, respectively. On the contrary, Flannel is consistently the lowest resource intensive solution, with comparable throughput performance to Antrea, Cilium and K-ovn plugins. Cilium, the only eBPF-based plugin, seems to maintain a lower CPU consumption compared to the Antrea and SDN-based plugins. Notably, the investigated plugins achieve their **maximum throughput under the NoEnc/HostGW**

tunnelling options i.e. in direct routing approaches, due to the lack of additional overhead, however, this option leads to an increased CPU utilization.

Figure 18 depicts the findings of the tunnelling scenario considering UDP connection. As shown, results maintain a similar pattern to this of the TCP connection type. Regarding the comparison between the TCP and UDP connection types, a comparable RAM consumption is revealed for both types, while UDP results on an increased CPU consumption.

Figure 19: Security/Encryption options of vanilla K8s plugins for CPU, RAM usage and Throughput - p2p TCP scenario

Figure 20: Security/Encryption options of vanilla K8s plugins for CPU, RAM usage and throughput - p2p UDP scenario.

Security/Encryption scenario: Figure 19 shows the performance trade-offs of the security and encryption mechanisms within each plugin, for TCP communication. Calico consistently outperforms the rest of the involved plugins in terms of throughput, even in the eBPF option (which is not its default option), also providing higher resource expenses (as shown in the tunnelling scenario). Regarding the resource consumption of the different security options, WG concludes with higher CPU rates for all considered plugins, i.e., between 40-50%. On the other hand, IPsec and Istio options result in approximately 30% and 10-20% CPU consumption, respectively. In addition, insignificant deviations in the RAM consumption are shown for the given security/encryption options. Focusing on eBPF in Cilium (default), we observe the lowest CPU consumption and better RAM performance.

Regarding the results over the UDP communication, as depicted in Figure 20, eBPF and Istio achieve higher throughput gains compared to WG and IPsec, while maintaining a comparable resource consumption to them. Note that, in accordance to Figure 19, WG remains the most CPU consuming option. The UDP's degraded throughput can be attributed to the hardware offloading conditions.

Figure 21: Service mesh/Observability options of MK8s plugins for CPU, RAM usage and Throughput - p2p TCP scenario.

Figure 22: Service mesh/Observability options of MK8s plugins for CPU, RAM usage and Throughput - p2p UDP scenario.

Service mesh/Observability scenario: Figure 21 depicts the different Service mesh/Observability options over the MK8s distribution, for the TCP communication. As shown, Flannel outperforms Calico and Kube-ovn plugins in terms of throughput, while keeping a lower CPU and RAM consumption compared to Kube-ovn. On the other hand, Calico emerges as the most lightweight solution in this scenario. Furthermore, all plugins provide similar performance for the given service mesh/observability. Lastly, comparing the results of Istio in MicroK8s and K8s we observe that Calico and Flannel reduce further their RAM consumption by 35% and 15%, demonstrating their adaptability in this lightweight distribution. However, Calico's throughput is reduced due to this adaptation. Regarding the UDP communication, shown in Figure 22, Kube-ovn achieves the highest throughput at the cost of the highest resource utilization. On the other hand, the resource consumption of all plugins remains relatively similar to the TCP scenario.

Finally, we **summarize main insights of the overall experiment**, that may serve as a reference point for determining relevant implementation choices in real-world edge-cloud applications: i) the plugin's selection highly affects the performance of the plugin's tunnelling option, rather than the opposite; ii) regarding the security/encryption scenarios, specific options may be advantageous for resource constraint use-cases, e.g., WG when low CPU usage is mandatory. Additionally, Istio (as service mesh) and eBPF (as data plane) provide both higher performance and lower resource utilization rates in contrast to IPsec and WG, demonstrating their suitability in resource-constrained environments; iii) MK8s reduces the resource impact of the selected CNI plugins' features, as demonstrated by comparing Istio's performance on vanilla K8s and MK8s.

Scenario 3 – EdgeNet deployment and features.

Here, we demonstrate the capability of CODEF to handle complex edge system deployments, such as the installation of EdgeNet, an open-source solution designed to extend K8s to the Edge [9],[10]. Such process involves installing EdgeNet prerequisites, e.g., creates kubeconfig and SSH-key secret certificates, configures WG, creates CRs for VPN peering, and installs the EdgeNet features implemented as CR Definitions and operators. Such deployment required also improvements in the EdgeNet software itself, e.g., to improve its autonomic deployment, compatibility and versioning.

After the installation, a functional CODECO-EdgeNet K8s cluster is deployed, with supported functionalities, such as: i) Multi-tenancy: role-based approach in the shared cluster, e.g., create and accept tenant and role requests, create slices, sub namespaces, allocate resource quotas, etc.; and ii) Multi-provider: users from around the world can contribute nodes (VMs or physical ones) to the cluster, with a single command.

Figure 23 illustrates the output of some basic *kubect* commands, showcasing the successful installation of EdgeNet software, the establishment of the cluster, and the node contribution processes.

```
athena@athml:~$ kubectl get nodes -o wide
```

NAME	STATUS	ROLES	AGE	VERSION	INTERNAL-IP	OS-IMAGE	KERNEL-VERSION
athml	Ready	control-plane, master	28h	v1.23.17	83.2	Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS	5.15.0-71-generic
athw2	Ready	<none>	28h	v1.23.17	83.2	Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS	5.15.0-71-generic
athw3	Ready	<none>	28h	v1.23.17	83.2	Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS	5.15.0-71-generic
gr-a-7230.edge-net.io	Ready	<none>	15m	v1.23.17	83.2	Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS	5.15.0-86-generic
gr-b-89c3.edge-net.io	Ready	<none>	108s	v1.23.17	195.2	Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS	5.15.0-71-generic
gr-b-abf4.edge-net.io	Ready	<none>	3m26s	v1.23.17	195.2	Ubuntu 22.04.2 LTS	5.15.0-71-generic


```
athena@athml:~$ kubectl get nodecontributions
```

NAME	ADDRESS	PORT	ENABLED	STATUS	AGE
gr-a-7230	83.2	22	true	Node Accessed	16m
gr-b-89c3	195.2	22	true	Node Accessed	2m34s
gr-b-abf4	195.2	22	true	Node Accessed	4m13s

Figure 23: EdgeNet installation and node contribution output commands.

Scenario 4 - Assessment of anomaly detection (AD) workflows tailored for edge environments.

In this last scenario, we demonstrate CODEF's capabilities to pragmatically assess the performance of AD algorithms in real-world Kubernetes-based edge cloud deployments, which may offer critical insights and trade-offs between theoretical properties of algorithms (e.g., detection delay in data points) and their impact on edge cloud resources (e.g., resource consumption or response time).

The AD methods are implemented as K8s Argo workflows (operated/removed on demand) and use a client-server application. The experimental parameters are defined through the workflows, e.g., the type of the AD method and the number of simultaneous clients to be deployed. The client-server communication is achieved through a REST API. The client transmits, in real-time, new data samples to the server, which employs the AD mechanisms and alerts the clients for anomalies. The servers also monitor the resource consumption of the AD mechanisms using an extension of the KNB tool. This setup allows the specification of an experiment configuration with the details of AD workflows (e.g., number of clients, cluster node affinity, etc.), mechanisms (e.g., type and configuration), as well as of communicated and

processed data (e.g., out of a trace-file or generated from known distributions/time-series models).

Here, we focus on the evaluation of the following 3 online AD detectors: i) standard CUSUM detector (tCUSUM) [12]; ii) ARMA-based CUSUM (pCUSUM) [13]; and iii) restarted Bayesian (rBOCP) [14]. Note that, additional AD mechanisms may also be included as containerized MATLAB functions within the evaluation framework. Results are assessed over 100 Monte Carlo simulations and the experiments were replicated in both UoM (t1) and ATH (t2) testbeds.

Figure 24: i) actual DD versus DD in data points, ii) memory versus CPU consumption, and iii) response time for each time-series, assuming 1 client, in both UoM (first row) and ATH (second row) testbeds.

Figure 24 shows the metrics: i) actual DD, ii) DD in data points, iii) memory and CPU utilization in percentage (%); and iii) the response time (in ms), for all three CP procedures, in t1 (first row) and t2 (second row) testbeds, assuming that 1 client utilizes the service. As shown, by expanding the evaluation metrics, CODEF offers practitioners valuable insights into the performance of AD methods in real-world edge applications, insights that typical statistical metrics fail to reveal. For instance, when comparing BOCP with the online CUSUM procedures, the first concludes on a substantially higher actual detection gap in msec, despite providing the shortest detection gap in data points (Figures 24a and 24d). Moreover, we observe a linear relationship between the actual DD and DD measured in data points, with BOCP and pCUSUM displaying greater fluctuations (due to the complexity of the detectors). Figures 24b and 24e illustrate the CPU and memory consumption of each CP method, the npCUSUM method exhibits superior performance in terms of both CPU and memory consumption, followed by the pCUSUM, with the BOCD method exhibiting the higher resource demands. Note that, despite the fluctuations in the CPU utilization between the two testbeds, an almost stable performance is indicated for the examined methods in terms of resource utilization. This implies that the CP detectors exhibit a degree of independency in relation to the physical machine configuration (i.e., the algorithms use the same number of resources in the virtual space). Consequently, the mechanisms may be characterized by a relatively stable resource footprint, which can be valuable to Kubernetes resource-optimization tasks (e.g., elasticity). Finally, Figures 24c and 24f, illustrate that the response times for each method remain relatively stable in both testbeds, with minimal variation, especially in the case of the

npCUSUM method. Note that, the higher variation in response time regarding to the BOCD procedure, reflects to the variation of the actual DD for similar DD in data points.

Figure 25: Mean: i) actual DD, ii) response time, iii) CPU consumption, and iv) memory consumption, in UoM (t1) and ATHENA (t2) testbeds, regarding $k = \{1, \dots, 5\}$ clients.

Subsequently, Figure 25 illustrates the mean actual DD, response time, and CPU and memory utilization, for $k = \{1, \dots, 5\}$ clients served simultaneously. Concerning the actual DD in Figure 3a, we observe that an increase in the number of clients mainly affects pCUSUM and BOCD, resulting in a 2 to 4 times increase in the actual DD, when compared to the scenario with one client. On the other hand, npCUSUM shows a relative stable performance irrespective of the number of clients to be processed. This result is also confirmed by the corresponding measurements of the response times in Figure 25b. In addition, in Figure 25c and 25d, we identify an increase in the resource consumption of the CP procedures, which, however, retain distinct characteristics in terms of CPU and memory utilization. This fact may be attributed to the initiation and termination of pods that temporarily impact CPU performance, i.e., this may be significant in the cases with a larger number of clients and a short experiment duration. However, this aspect requires further investigations, e.g., to decouple algorithmic resource consumption from pod manipulation overhead. Nevertheless, BOCD exhibits a superior performance in terms of CPU consumption. Interestingly, the increase in the resource consumption of npCUSUM does not impact its actual DD, due to its very lightweight algorithm.

Summarizing, our **main insights regarding the performance evaluation of AD mechanisms** over edge-cloud environments, follow: i) the typical trade-off between false alarm and detection delay is not sufficient to characterize the performance of CP mechanisms in real AD applications, especially of those deployed at the edge, and ii) the employed detectors provide a discrete resource utilization behavior, with slight variations within each method, which is also maintained across both testbeds. This observation intuitively suggests that resource consumption may exhibit some degree of predictability, which is an important input for resource optimization mechanisms.

8 Summary and Next Steps

The CODECO Deliverable D17 outlines the work carried out between months 7 and 24 of the CODECO project within WP5, with a focus on the development of the CODEF by ATH. It provides a comprehensive overview of CODEF's design, architecture, and workflow, emphasizing its abstraction layers that enhance flexibility, along with examples and code for its use. The deliverable details the rationale for replacing EdgeNet with CODEF and explores its alignment with global and European edge-cloud experimentation initiatives.

Additionally, it highlights CODEF's role in validating CODECO, including deployment in the AWS CODECO shared cloud, and describes the validation procedures for CODECO components and OSS. CODEF's contributions to large-scale experimentation across diverse environments are emphasized, with evaluation plans, methodologies, and proof-of-concept implementations showcasing its capabilities and integration with CODECO OSS.

The primary next step for CODEF is to **transition from development to active utilization by project partners**. This involves using CODEF to conduct experiments, enhance collaborative works and validate CODECO across heterogeneous infrastructures and diverse scenarios. By leveraging CODEF's capabilities, CODECO can deploy real-world applications, address complex challenges and ensure robustness, adaptability and scalability, while achieving the agreed KPIs in WP5. Furthermore, the active utilization of CODEF will help elevate the framework to a new TRL, establishing it as a key tool for edge-cloud experimentation.

Through its flexible Resource Managers and custom Ansible playbooks, CODEF can **extend its support for a broader range of software and applications**, allowing the integration of CODEF with future CODECO enhancements. In this regard, while CODEF currently follows a single-cluster approach, it will **support multi-cluster experimentation processes**, particularly within federated cluster objectives of WP4. In particular, CODEF can deploy advanced multi-cluster solutions like OCM and integrate networking tools like Karmada or Ligo to enable cross-cluster communication. Moreover, CODEF is already installed in the CODECO shared cloud space (rf. to Section 6.1).

One of the under-deployments CODEF's valuable features is its ability to **support node contributions**, a feature not widely adopted by other open-source initiatives. Thus, CODEF can empower partners to share resources dynamically, fostering collaboration. This focus on node contribution strengthens the platform's appeal for use cases requiring distributed resource sharing and experimentation, not only within the CODECO project but as a CODECO asset for future endeavours as well. Other next steps for CODEF include:

- (iv) **enhancing its support for parallel execution**, allowing for more efficient and scalable experiments.
- (iv) **extending ML capabilities**, to bring intelligent automation, predictive modelling and adaptive decision-making. These features will significantly enhance CODEF's utility for data-driven edge-cloud experimentation.
- (iv) **implementing robust security and cluster management features**, which have not been a primary focus until now. This will establish a trusted environment for conducting experiments, ensuring compliance with security standards.
- (iv) **introducing solutions for real-time checks and live debugging** to improve UE. While some of these capabilities are already partially implemented through the integration of tools like Jaeger, monitoring tools, debug visualizers and custom scripts, further will allow users to monitor experiments dynamically and troubleshoot issues.

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